

SONNET - SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS

Co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, success and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector

Towards a conceptual framework: Starting with our building blocks

Working paper 1.0

January 22nd, 2020

APPENDIX – SONNET RESEARCH BRIEFS

Overview Research Briefs

Research Brief #1: Avelino, Flor (2020) **A transformative social innovation perspective on the diversity, contributions and processes of social innovation.** SONNET Research Brief. SONNET: EU H2020 Grant Agreement 837498

Research Brief #2a: Hielscher, Sabine (2019) **New institutionalism: Examining the processes of social innovation initiatives.** SONNET Research Brief. SONNET: EU H2020 Grant Agreement 837498

Research Brief #2b: Hielscher, Sabine (2020) **Possible ways to explore the processes and contributions of SIE-initiatives.** SONNET Research Brief. SONNET: EU H2020 Grant Agreement 837498

Research Brief #3: Fraaije, M., Wittmayer, J.M. & T. de Geus (2020) **The empirical diversity of social innovation in energy.** SONNET Research Brief. SONNET: EU H2020 Grant Agreement 837498

Research Brief #4: Winzer, C., Schmid, B., Dzukowski, T. & D. Wemyss (2019) **Defining the success of social innovation in energy.** SONNET Research Brief. SONNET: EU H2020 Grant Agreement 837498

Research Brief #5: Marie-Charlotte Guetlein, Joachim Schleich (2019) **Insights on the future potentials of social innovations in energy.** SONNET Research Brief. SONNET: EU H2020 Grant Agreement 837498

Research Brief #6: Wittmayer, J.M., Dütschke, E., & M. Fraaije (2020) **Research brief on socio-cultural aspects of social innovation in energy – a first draft.** SONNET Research Brief. SONNET: EU H2020 Grant Agreement 837498

Research Brief #7: Stadler, M., Avelino, F., Brugger, H., Strumińska-Kutra, M. and K. Rogge (2020) **A socio-political focus on social innovation in energy: drivers, barriers and contributions.** SONNET Research Brief. SONNET: EU H2020 Grant Agreement 837498

Research Brief #8: Wemyss, D., Hielscher, S., Vernay, Ranville, Struminska, M. & A. Dembek (2019) **Research brief on socio-economic issues of social innovation in energy.** SONNET Research Brief. SONNET: EU H2020 Grant Agreement 837498

Research Brief #9: Struminska-Kutra, M., Dembek, A., Stasik, A. & B. Rok (2019) **City Labs.** SONNET: EU H2020 Grant Agreement 837498

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SONNET research brief #1: transformative social innovation perspective on the diversity, contributions and processes of social innovation.

Flor Avelino, 22.01.2020

A. A few thoughts/ reflections on doing the literature review

This brief so far is primarily based on insights on transformative social innovation from the Transformative Social Innovation Theory (TRANSIT) research project. It has not (yet) been updated with other more diverse literature on the relations between (social) innovation and transformative, institutional change.

B. What do we know from the literature?

Transformative social innovation is a concept that was developed at the intersection of transition research, social innovation studies and other social change theories, to question how, to what extent and under what conditions social innovations can contribute to transformative, systemic change. The concept of transformative social innovation has been defined as changing social relations involving new ways of doing, thinking and organising, which challenge, alter and/or replace dominant institutions in the social context (Haxeltine et al. 2017a, forthcoming, Avelino et al. 2019).

Transition research is a relatively new, interdisciplinary field of research that emerged out of a coalescence between various other 'interdisciplines', including innovation studies, science and technology studies, complexity theory and governance theory (Grin et al. 2010, Markard et al. 2012, Loorbach et al. 2017). Underlying these different backgrounds and perspectives, lies a shared focus on transitions: processes of long-term change in which the societal systems are structurally transformed. While the original focus of the field has been on socio-technical systems (e.g. transport, energy, agriculture, etc.), recent years have seen increasing attention for the more social and political aspects of transformative change. This includes explicit attention for topics of power and politics (Voß et al. 2009, Geels 2014, Avelino et al. 2016) and grassroots innovation (Seyfang & Smith 2007, Haxeltine & Seyfang 2012, Smith & Stirling 2018), as well as interlinkages with another emerging field focused on social innovation (Franz et al. 2012, Moulaert et al. 2017, Moulaert & McCallum 2019).

The distinction between 'innovation' and 'transformation' is particularly relevant. Although innovation can contribute to transitions at the level of societal systems, it does not necessarily do so. On the contrary, innovation can in fact be used to adapt and optimize the structures in existing systems, as such even hampering a transition in that system. This same logic has been followed in the conceptualisation of transformative social innovation. Social innovations are defined as ideas,

objects or activities that change social relations, involving new ways of doing, thinking and organising (Avelino et al. 2019). Such social innovations do not necessarily contribute to transitions or transformative change – they may be fact used to reproduce current structures and institutions. In line with transition theory, transformative change has been conceptualised as challenging, altering and/or replacing dominant institutions in the social context. We then argued that social innovation is transformative to the extent that it challenges, alters and/or replaces dominant institutions in the social context (Haxeltine et al. 2017a, forthcoming).

As such the transformative dimension is a gradual process characteristic of social innovation; rather than aiming to evaluate whether social innovations are inherently transformative or not, it is about exploring the extent to which they (can) challenge, alter and/or replace dominant institutions, and possibly comparing how, in that sense, some social innovation may be more or less transformative than others. In this process approach to transformative change we have also taken an explicitly dialectic perspective to acknowledge that even when social innovations are challenging (some aspects of) dominant institutions, they can meanwhile also reproduce (other aspects of) these or other dominant institutions (Pel 2016, Haxeltine et al. forthcoming).

Building on the fields of sustainability transitions, social innovation, and several other social change theories, the TRANSIT project developed a middle-range theory of transformative social innovation (TSI-theory). This middle-range TSI-theory was developed over a period of 4 years by 30+ researchers from 12 research institutes, through iterative formulations of propositions which were grounded, verified and adapted based on empirical observations and the comparative study of 20 social innovation networks and 100 associated initiatives (for more detail about how the theory was developed, see Haxeltine et al. 2017b, Haxeltine forthcoming). The resulting TSI-theory was developed along four 'clusters' of socio-material relations at four distinct levels of aggregation:

- 1) Relations within social innovation (SI) initiatives
- 2) Relations between SI-initiatives in network formation
- 3) Relations between SI-institutions and institutional change
- 4) Relations between SI-institutions and the socio-material context

For each of these clusters, three propositions were developed, resulting in a total of 12 propositions on TSI-processes:

Relations within social innovation (SI) initiatives

1. Proposition 1. SI initiatives provide spaces in which new or alternative values can be promoted and aligned with new knowledge and practices—in a process of reflexive experimentation that supports both members' motivations and their moves towards collective 'success' and 'impact'.

2. Proposition 2. Manifesting new/alternative interpersonal relations is one pivotal way in which SI actors are able to create the right conditions to challenge, alter, or replace dominant institutions.
3. Proposition 3: People are empowered to persist in their efforts towards institutional change, to the extent that basic needs for relatedness, autonomy, and competence are satisfied, while at the same time experiencing an increased sense of impact, meaning, and resilience.

Relations between SI-initiatives in network formation

4. Proposition 4: The transformative impacts of SI initiatives depend greatly on the changing tensions within and stability of the action field(s) that they operate in.
5. Proposition 5: Translocal networks are a key source of empowerment for local SI initiatives.
6. Proposition 6: Discourse formation and its mediation through communication infrastructures crucially enhances the reach of SI network formation.

Relations between SI-institutions and institutional change

7. Proposition 7. SI initiatives need to find an institutional home in order to access vital resources; this often entails a balancing against the desire for independence from (critiqued) dominant institutions and finding hybrid institutional forms.
8. Proposition 8. In order to bring about institutional change, SI initiatives need to combine different forms of institutional entrepreneurship, and proactively adapt these strategies in response to changing circumstances.
9. Proposition 9. SI initiatives reconsider and reconfigure the broader institutional logics in which dominant institutions are embedded, by learning across different institutional logics and by reinventing, recombining and transposing specific elements from one institutional logic to another.

Relations between SI-institutions and the socio-material context

10. Proposition 10. The rise of SI initiatives and their particular transformative ambitions are strongly shaped by the historical development of the wider socio-material context.
11. Proposition 11. SI initiatives are only innovative against the background of an evolving socio-material context. Activities of innovating and inventing present but one historical appearance of TSI, next to other less conspicuously innovative activities of re-invention, advocacy, and maintenance.

- 12. Proposition 12. Evolutionary diversity is an integral element of TSI processes, reflecting the historical diversity of the transformative ambitions of SI initiatives and the diverse motivations of the people involved in them.

Figure 1 below schematically summarizes the four clusters as well as the main topics of each of the 12 propositions.

- TSI = interface of transition studies & social innovation

Figure 1. Transformative social innovation processes across 4 types of social relations

C. What are the research gaps?

Given the relatively newness of the concept of 'transformative social innovation', there are many research gaps and opportunities for future research. For the purpose of this brief, we focus on specific research gaps that the SONNET project seems to have potential to fill.

- The TRANSIT project explicitly defined SI in terms of changing social relations and explored this 'relational perspective' regarding socio-material entanglements between processes of doing, thinking and organizing at different levels of aggregation. However, what it did not do is deepen and elaborate different types of social relations and social interactions.
- The TRANSIT project distinguished between transformative ambition, potential and impact, but did not deepen these distinctions. Empirically, it focused on ambition/intentions of initiatives, and on analysing processes without being specific on the extent to which it aimed to evaluate potential and/or impact.
- Although the TRANSIT project defined TSI in terms of institutional change and included references to institutional change theory, there is a lot of room to further elaborate and diversify insights on institutional change from e.g. institutional work, field theory, institutional logics, hybrid institutions etc.
- Empirically, the TRANSIT project focused primarily on analysing SI-initiatives and networks and much less so on the dominant institutions, the system context and on understanding the 'actual' 'countervailing' impact of SI on those dominant institutions and their networks.
- The notion of power is implicitly present in TSI-theory, primarily in the concepts of changing social relations, processes of (dis)empowerment and the challenging of dominant institutions. One particular research gap concerns more explicit attention for shifting power dynamics as one type of social relation and how it changes, building on social and political power theories.
- The TRANSIT project stressed that SI is not necessarily 'good' and decoupled the definition of SI from its societal outcome. TRANSIT's empirical case-studies included a description of the normative ambitions and intentions of SI-initiatives and networks. However, the project did not deepen and analyse the normative directionalities of (T)SI in a wider societal context (Pel et al. 2019).
- Related to the issue of directionalities and normativity, more research is necessary to analyse the narrative and discursive dimensions of TSI. While the TRANSIT project did include a conceptualisation of 'narratives of change' and empirically analysis how SI-initiatives and networks developed such narratives, it did not yet relate this to wider discourse analysis in the societal context.
- While the TRANSIT project did bridge the fields of sustainability transitions and social innovation at a conceptual level, it mostly did so by focusing on an intermediary process concept of 'transformative change'. It did not come up with clear propositions and analysis of how and to what extent social innovation (can) contribute to sustainability transitions.
- In the TRANSIT project, there was no empirical focus on a particular sector/domain and – partly as a result of that – the 'socio-material context' has remained an under-conceptualised and under-studied unit of analysis. This is where TSI-theory could benefit

from (1) perspectives that provide tools for system analysis (e.g. regime analysis, field analysis), and (2) an empirical focus on particular sector/domain such as energy.

Many of the research gaps identified above are highly interrelated and filling one gap is expected to greatly facilitate the tackling of other gaps. SONNET's focus on energy, for instance, can greatly facilitate more attention for the socio-material context, to analyze (the impact of SI on) institutions and discourses, and to analyze the contribution of SI to a specific 'sustainability transition' including its diverse normative directionalities.

D. What questions arise for SONNET?

We now turn to reflect on SONNET's main building blocks from a TSI perspective, with a focus on specifying certain questions and suggestions for analyzing social innovation in energy (SIE) in relation to sustainability transitions

Diversity

- Definition of SI as changing social relations, involving new ways of doing, thinking, organising, means that SI is – by definition – very diverse.
- Relational and socio-material perspective implies looking at diverse units of analysis, not only social ones, but also material ones and socio-material hybrids. So including ideas, actions as well as objects (technologies, ecological factors).
- While the boundaries of 'energy' provide opportunities to fill many research gaps, as pointed out above, there is also a risk of excluding phenomena that could be particularly innovative or transformative. Reframing 'energy' and its related issues in terms of non-energy terms (e.g. focus on 'resources' or 'circularity') may well be a manifestation of social innovation or even transformative change, but be missed out for a lack of focus on 'energy'.
- Translocal connections and diversity implies attention for SI in both urban and rural contexts as well as the socio-material connections in urban-rural linkages. Given SONNET's focus on cities it is important to either acknowledge this bias or to still include attention for rural and urban-rural SIE.

Processes

- One way in which the TRANSIT project has looked at (T)SI-processes is through the notion and method of Critical Turning Points (CTP), which is also taken up in the SONNET work plan.
- In a focus on processes and CTPs, it is important to look at those not only from the perspective of the SIs and SI-initiatives, but to also look at them from the perspective of institutions/ fields/ systems and transitions. Otherwise SONNET runs the risk of reproducing the same research gaps that TRANSIT did.
- We should not only look at the process of how SI develops and then may affect institutions, but also the other way around, how institutions develop and may affect SI. I.e. the co-evolutionary processes between institutional change and emergence of SI.

Contributions: Success, Impact & Potential

- The very notions of success and impact, and the specific ways in which they are framed in a particular context, are to a great extent socially constructed according to certain narratives and theories of change. As such it is relevant to understand not only what the indicators of success are at a specific point in time or according to a certain context, but also to understand how these were constructed on how they relate to different directionalities in energy transitions (Pel et al. 2019)
- In the wider societal discourse on social innovation there seems to be quite a lot of attention for the notion of 'impact'. There is even talk of the 'social impact economy' and initiatives like the *Impact Hub* (one of TRANSIT's case-studies) shape a significant part of their identity around innovation and positive impact. There is also quite some critique on this "obsession with impact" (e.g. De Geus 2018), which is relevant for us to be aware about and to relate to.
- Some scholars might argue that there is an inherent tension between notions such as success and impact on the one hand, and the relational perspective on the other hand. For SONNET it is important to clarify how we see this tension. To we aim to synthesise, or rather accept them as two separate aspects of the project?
- SONNET needs to be aware of and engage with the academic and public debate around 'impact' and evaluation more generally. In the TRANSIT project there has been also work done on diverse forms of monitoring and evaluation (Kemp et al. 2017, Weaver et al. 2017) which may be relevant here.
- To analyse the future potential of SIE can focus on any of these three: intentions/ambitions for the future, potential processes as well as potential impacts.
- If SONNET studies success, positive impact and positive future potential of SIE, it should also study (or at least acknowledge) failure, negative impact and future potential risks, including the unintended consequences of SIE.

E. What are key readings?

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Research Brief #2a: New institutionalism: Examining the processes of social innovation initiatives.

Hielscher, Sabine, 2019

A. Research briefing's relationship to SONNET

Drawing on **sustainability transitions research and taking a socio-institutional perspective**, SONNET recognizes that there is a need to understand the **processes of SIE as 'innovation journeys'** rather than static entities. This allows SONNET to investigate the **dynamic interactions between SIE and broader institutional dynamics towards transformative change** (McGowan and Westley, 2015; Haxeltine et al., 2017). Therefore, SONNET does not only analyse SIE-initiatives (e.g. a novel energy cooperative) but also dominant institutions in the energy sector (e.g. existing regulations, routines, practises, ways of thinking, social norms on how to consume and produce energy), as these can enable and impede SIE. SIE-initiatives interact with these dominant institutions through institutional work (e.g. creating novel ways of thinking about energy, i.e. such as ideas of prosumption and decentralised energy) to further energy transitions (for a more detailed outline see second building block of conceptual framework in proposal).

SONNET's focus on institutions rests both on the sustainability transitions and the social innovation literatures. The former uses the notion of long-term transformative change which captures the idea that fundamental changes to current dominant institutional arrangements within the energy systems are needed to prevent threats such as climate change and resource deprivation (Weber and Rohracher, 2012). Within the latter, institutional dynamics, among others, are argued to be key in explaining social innovation processes (Cajaiba-Santana (2014) and van der Have & Rubalcaba (2016)). **Institutions** are understood as rule-like 'social facts', as 'systems of established and embedded social rules that structure social interactions' (Hodgson, 2006). In addition, Scott (2008:22) has differentiated institutions into 'regulative, normative and cultural-cognitive' elements that, together with associated activities and resources, provide stability and meaning to social life.

As social innovations develop over time and space, they transform institutions (e.g. normative beliefs around how energy is produced), while at the same time they also inevitably reproduce them (e.g. gender issues i.e. mainly men getting involved in setting up energy cooperatives). Lawrence and Suddaby (2006) have drawn on the **notion of institutional work** to explain deliberate activities of individuals and/or organisations that aim to create, maintain and transform institutions. SIE-initiatives create, maintain and transform institutions through several activities. Most develop novel business and services models, organisational and governance structures, and financial models that are grounded in collaborative processes and collective outcomes (Walker & Devine-Wright, 2008). To gain better insights into SIE processes, SONNET studies the institutional work of SIE-initiatives focusing specifically on its transformative nature to enable sustainable energy transitions.

B. Reflections on conducting the review

This research briefing has two aims: 1) examine how the current literature on SIE (represented in the SONNET literature database) conceptualizes institutions and their relations to SIE, and 2) develop the teams understanding of institutions and institutional work, drawing on the literature of new institutionalism.

C. What do we know from the literature?

1. SONNET database literature review on institutions

The term 'institutions' is used quite broadly in articles within the SONNET database. The term is often used to describe particular actor groups, actor logics/ powers, processes or 'contextual conditions'.

- Actors: social institution (i.e. church, family), institutional actors (i.e. cities and counties – often actors related to the state/ government), ‘institutional entrepreneurship’ (Mahzouni 2019), institutional intermediaries (i.e. government affiliated) and their logics/ powers: ‘institutional logics’ (Bauwens et al. 2019), ‘institutionalising powers’ (Sareen et al. 2018).
- Processes: ‘institutional adaption’ (Warbroek et al. 2017), Thompson et al. 1996), ‘institutional mechanisms’ (Shpykuliak et al. 2019), initiatives becoming ‘more institutionalised’ (Giugni et al. 2015), institutional practices (Thompson et al.) and ‘institutional change’ (Fox 2013).
- ‘Contextual conditions’: institutional lock-in (Melville et al.), ‘institutional conditions’ (Hyysalo et al. 2018), ‘institutional structure’ (Holstenkamp 2019)... and related ‘institutional barriers’ (Mey et al. 2016; Hissenmoeller et al. 2013), ‘institutional issues’ (Moroni et al. 2018), ‘institutional support’ (Kivimaa et al. 2019), ‘institutional incentives’ (Gorrone-Albizu 2019), ‘institutional factors’ (Warnecke et al. 2016).

For instance, Eadson et al. acknowledge institutional conditions (rules, metrics, instruments, incentives and so on) and governmental tools within developments of community energy, whilst examining the politics of market constructions. Bauwens emphasises the role of institutions (i.e. formal and informal rules that shape and structure the interactions between people within collective settings) as important factors for understanding the heterogeneity of RE investors, examining the motivations of people to invest in community RE. Mignon et al (2016) makes use of the notion of ‘hard’ and ‘soft’ institutions to compare country settings and RE cooperative projects. “Hard and soft institutions are the formal and informal rules and norms that exist with in an institutional context. Formal rules, such as existing laws, regulations, standards, and informal norms and values, for instance public perceptions or acceptance of an innovation may hinder or slow down the deployment of innovations.”

The use of the terms related to ‘institutions’ is frequently not defined but taken for granted. It sometimes feels that the terms ‘incumbency’/ institutions are used interchangeably. It might be interesting to have a look whether this is the case and investigate the boundaries of these to notions.

Empirical work that makes use of the notion of institutions can be divided in the following ‘groups’: 1) *conflicts and interactions between energy initiatives and existing institutions* e.g. Proka et al. (2018) look at the transformative potentials of Dutch energy initiatives, examining destabilisation and conflict between the incumbent regime and energy initiatives. Energy initiatives deal with given institutional context imposed by incumbent energy regime. They deal with them through the following notions: fit and conform/ stretch and transform (as outline by Smith et al.); 2) *shaping of the emergence and development of energy initiatives through the existing institutional context* e.g. Koirala et al. (2016), Hasanov et al. (2018) & Mignon et al. (2016) investigate ‘institutional issues shaping’ energy and the ‘institutional context’ in which they emerge & Ahl et al. (2019) studies how current ‘institutional change’ in the energy system creates opportunities for energy initiatives.; 3) *embedding of energy initiatives over time* e.g. Wolsink (2012) examines ‘new systems [initiatives and their activities] become institutionally embedded’ & Pacheco et al. 2014 investigate the co-evolutions of initiatives, industries and institutions over time. Drawing on the Polanyi’s work of the great transformation and notion of double movement, Eadson et al. (2019) investigate the heterogeneous ‘logics’ (e.g. market) at work within energy transitions from initiatives to states, considering political process as ontologically performative.

For instance, Wolsink (2012) argues that “we may recognize five categories of institutions that may result in lock-ins: • government policies – interventions, legal frameworks, government organization in departments, ministries and agencies; • dominant technologies – including standardization; • organizational routines and relations; • industry standards and specializations; • societal expectations and preferences.”

Conceptual work mentions the following frameworks/ perspectives: *Historical institutionalist approaches* (Ferguson-Martin 2011), *Institutional theory perspectives* (Mey et al. 2018) & (Hoicka et al. 2018) & (Wirth 2014), *Institutional analysis and development framework* (Koster et al. 2013), and *New institutional economic* (Gui et al. 2017).

Historical institutionalist approaches (Ferguson-Martin 2011)

“In the context of wind energy, institutions are “decision-making structures, forms of organizations of wind power, planning systems and norms and agreements, which underpin wind power policy and practise” (Toke et al. 2008). Historical institutionalism recognizes that institutions can evolve or change over time due to functionalist, cultural and political factors and that a path dependency to these changes can exist. We suggest that structural and technological factors such as electricity infrastructure and the historical use of particular energy technologies may also influential in shaping institutions.” – see also Toke et al. 2008 about this approach.

Institutional theory perspectives (Mey et al. 2018) & (Wirth 2014) & (Barnes et al. 2018)

Some of the articles are already grounded in neo-institutionalism (Scott 2008) as outlined in the SONNET proposal...

“We use an organizational and institutional theory perspective following Fligstein and Mc Adam’s concept of strategic action fields.” “The strategic action field’s approach is concerned with stability and change in meso-level orders of social life. Originating in the works of Bourdieu [44], Bourdieu [45], Meyer and Rowan [46], DiMaggio and Powell [47], DiMaggio [48], Scott [49] and Fligstein and McAdam [11], the approach focuses on interactions of individual and/or collective actors based on a mutual understanding of the purpose and the rules that characterise a field. Following Fligstein and McAdam [11], the field is composed of incumbent and challenger actors who determine the field dynamics. These actors hold opposing positions and disparate resources: incumbents are characterised by wielding disproportional influence shaping the character of the field whereas challengers occupy niches with an alternative vision of the field. (Mey et al. 2018)

Wirth (2014) examines ‘community’ as its own institutional order i.e. community institutions, examining and drawing on cultural-cognitive, regulatory and normative institutional orders. He tries to argue that ‘informal’ institutions matter (e.g. values, belief systems).

Barnes et al. (2018) also discuss processes of institutionalisation but mainly link to literatures grounded in transition studies (rather than going back to new institutionalism), “we mobilise theory on institutionalisation processes and insights from the politics of transitions literature and take an actor perspective to investigate the agency of local sustainability initiatives to navigate local governance processes and reconfigure selection environments at the urban scale.”

Co-evolutionary institutional perspective (Kooij et al. 2018) & (Hoicka et al. 2018)

“Following other co-evolutionary approaches [27,28], our perspective recognizes the evolution of systems and the effect their evolutions have upon other co-evolving systems. Because this paper deals with the understanding of the role of GIs within a regulated energy system, we introduce and distinguish three dimensions, based on the impact these dimensions have on GIs [see also 18,29]. The material-economic dimension, the actor-institutional dimension and the discursive dimension constantly evolve and influence each other. For example, institutions are being shaped in co-evolution with actors, and institutions simultaneously shape actors [12,28,30–32]. This study takes a co-evolutionary institutional perspective, in which institutions are defined as the ‘rules of the game’ [33] including formal and informal rules, which coordinate governance and in turn can be altered through

interaction [34].” (Kooij et al. 2018)

“Institutional structures are consolidated forms of interaction of networking activities, or social conditions to which agents seek to take strategic action. Through these actions, institutional structures are being created, enforced or altered, transforming the existing institutional setting. Such a co-evolutionary understanding enables us to analyze the changes and interactions of material-economic configurations with actor-institution configurations, in relation to an understanding of power relations and the use of knowledge [31,36]. The institutional structure offers ‘conditions of possibility’: while it does not cause the emergence of GIs, it may provide institutional characteristics that enable GIs to develop activities or influence the institutional structure.” (Kooij et al. 2018)

“While the rise of individualized prosumers and micro-grids are widely discussed today in energy policy circles and beyond, the institutional and political underpinnings of transitions remain vague and underdeveloped at present.” (Hoicka et al .)

Institutional analysis and development framework (Koster et al. 2013) – cannot get access to book chapter

New institutional economic (Gui et al. 2017 [Bauwens et al 2016 also make use of Ostrom’s work])
 “We offer an institutional development framework for community microgrids using a New Institutional Economics (NIE) [drawing on the work of Ostrom] approach to address non-technical properties in the development of community microgrids, including property rights, asset characteristics, customer-provider relationship, ownership, governance and contractual arrangements... This framework provides a theoretical base of analyzing the structure of transactions and their governing institutions. Three key concepts – explicitly transaction costs, property rights and contracts – form the basic building blocks of the NIE, and are powerful tools for illuminating strategic behaviour; organizational arrangements; modes of governance; control and enforcement; and credible commitments.”

2. Different institutionalism: Four schools

Andrews-Speed () has summarised the four schools of institutionalism (directly copied):

The three long-standing schools of institutionalism can be identified [9,10]. *Rational choice institutionalism* builds on the assumption that actors are rational. However, the rationality of the actors is bounded and institutions provide incentives or rules that fulfil a vital role in lowering transaction costs and creating order [3,4]. Although rational choice institutionalism has its roots in economics, it has also been applied to political history [55].

Historical institutionalism developed within political science and focuses on how the wider structure of the polity or political economy shapes the distribution of power and the nature of power relations. This school takes a wider view on the nature of institutions, and includes both formal and informal rules, as well as norms, routines and ideas. It also shows how institutions not only constrain change but also themselves are resistant to change, a situation that results in most political change being incremental and path-dependent [56,57].

Sociological institutionalism grew from the field of sociology, as its name implies, and emphasizes the importance of culture in determining the nature of institutions and the way in which they shape actor behaviour. In this approach, institutions include symbols, frames and values that determine a set of practices that are specific to a particular culture and may have no relationship to economic efficiency. In other words, appropriateness trumps performance. These ideas have also been applied to

organizational studies and thus the terms 'sociological institutionalism' and 'organizational institutionalism' can be used interchangeably [58,59].

Finally, Schmidt [10] has proposed that *discursive institutionalism* be recognized a distinct approach that directs greater attention than the other three institutionalisms to the role of ideas and discourse in shaping political outcomes and institutional change.

No sharp boundaries exist between the four schools of thought and a number of ideas can be found in two or more forms of institutionalism. Three integrative schemes are particularly useful to the current study. In the field of sociological or organizational institutionalism, Scott [58,60] built on the earlier work of DiMaggio and Powell [59] to draw attention to the usefulness of organizational fields to analysing economic and business activity. An organizational field comprises a set of organizations interacting in a system that spans the full length of the supply chain, as well as customers and regulators. It is characterized by a particular set of rules, networks, relations, habits, frames and meanings; in other words, the organizational field is governed by a set of institutional logics. This approach also incorporates 'artefacts' or technologies as important institutional carriers.

(He also provides an in-depth comparison between these four schools and the use of institutions in transition studies. He argues for combining all four and outlines several empirical questions to explore institutional change in the conclusions.)

3. New institutionalism: Brief literature review (outside of SONNET database)

Diverse organisations involved in current energy systems are subject to broader social pressures from their institutional environment (Meyer and Rowan 1977, Di Maggio/Powell 1983). In order to receive support and legitimacy, organizations have to conform to overarching rules and requirements (such as energy regulations, standards) (Scott 1995). Taken into account current energy transitions developments in Europe, it becomes apparent that these rules and requirements are part of major changes that require organizations to undergo several adaptation processes which could potentially hugely influence their current day-to-day operations, collaborations with actors and business models (e.g. Stephens et al. 2015, Moss und Gailing 2016). On the other hand, it has been found that organizations do not accept these changes without at least some resistance and actively attempt to shape related negotiation processes and new role allocations (Stephens et al. 2015).

SONNET'S focus on institutions rests in parts on the social innovation literature. Cajaiba-Santana (2014) has argued that an investigation of how actors enable and frame the institutionalisation of new ideas and practices is key to explain social innovation processes. Institutions are understood as 'systems of established and embedded social rules that structure social interactions' (Hodgson, 2006:2) and not only capture single rules and laws but 'multifaceted, durable social structures, made up of symbolic elements, social activities and material resources' (Scott, 2001:49). SONNET does not only analyse SIE initiatives but also dominant institutional arrangements (e.g. existing regulations and routines) that influence the processes and contribution of SIE. As social innovations develop over time and space, they can transform dominant institutions, while at the same time they inevitably reproduce and/or are captured by them.

To be able to examine these institutional changes, the SONNET project team draws on neo-institutionalism (in addition to the work on institutionalisation within the social innovation literature). Work on neo-institutionalism has focused on developing a sociological view of institutions with a particular emphasis on examining institutional environments (including rules and requirements) and

the activities of organizations within a particular organizational field (DiMaggio/Powell 1983). At the centre of these conceptual developments are questions that examine the varying institutions that structure the organizational field and ways in which different organizations influence (and are influenced) by institutional changes (Möllering 2011). We could make use of the following three concepts: 1. Pillars of institutions (Scott 2008), 2. Organizational field (DiMaggio/Powell 1991) & issue-based field (), and 3. Institutional change (Leblebici et al. 1991, Hoffmann 1999) through institutional work (Lawrence & Suddaby 2006).

Pillars of institutions

Institutions have been defined as 'regulative, normative and cultural-cognitive elements that, together with associated activities and resources, provide stability and meaning to social life' (Scott 2008: 56). Scott (2001) has conceptualized institutions as three pillars that constitute and regulate social interactions: first, legally enforced i.e. regulative institutions, and second and third, informal but taken-for-granted i.e. normative, and cultural-cognitive institutions. Each of the pillars has their own basis of legitimacy and logic of compliance (Scott 2001, Raven et al. 2017). The regulative pillar describes the explicit regulative aspects of institutions. Rules, laws, policies, standards, control and sanctions are the key elements and mechanisms of compliance that give meaning to these institutions.

The normative pillar makes up the prescriptive, evaluative, and obligatory dimensions of institutions. This pillar is connected to values, social norms, duties, and role expectations i.e. what is considered appropriate behaviour and can be directed at all actors of a particular field (Scott 2001). Not complying with such norms and values can create strong emotional responses of, for instance, disgrace. Debates surrounding energy transitions are signified by differing expectations of what type of energy challenges might mitigate, for instance, economic, infrastructural, social and/or ecological. Which goals how more legitimacy than others still is highly debated between actors. The third pillar in Scott's conceptualization of institutions is the cultural-cognitive one. This pillar relates to the shared conceptions and frames with which the world is interpreted or meaning is given such as symbols, discourses and cultural categories. Such elements are usually implicit, as they frequently become routine ways of understanding the world and create 'cognitive logics' for action. They sometimes become more present when actors attempt to make sense of their routine behaviours. The cultural-cognitive pillar of institutions can entail, for example, and analysis of how actors frame and define energy transitions in relation to contemporary energy challenges.

An institutional perspective allows us to understand several change processes: a) the emergence of new organizations, b) changing legal and administrative structures, and c) changing belief systems (Beckert et al. 2016: 23).

Issue-based field / Organizational field

Organizational fields have been conceptualized as a group of organizations that 'in the aggregate constitute a recognised area of institutional life: key supplier, resource and product consumers, regulatory agencies, and other organizations that produce similar services or products' (DiMaggio and Powell 1991:64). Some shared meanings and norms can be recognised through informal and formal rules, values, assumptions about the world, and all forms of knowledge that are of importance for the actors in the organizational field. DiMaggio and Powell's (1991) definition of organizational fields includes organizations that are in competition with each other, as well as, organization that are integrated in similar meaning systems. Similarly, Hoffman (1999:352) has argued to not 'define a field around companies with a common product or market' but that a 'field is formed around issues that

become important to the interests and objectives of a specific collective of organizations'. For instance, within the field organizations can 'compete over the definition of issues and the form of institutions that will guide the organizations behaviour' (Hoffmann 1999: 352).

"Organizational fields arise when organizations partake of a common meaning system and increase inter-organizational activity, information exchange and mutual awareness (Di Maggio and Powell, 1983, Hoffman, 1999, Scott, 2008). Issue-based fields are distinct from common conceptions of organizational fields as they are "not formed around common technologies or common industries, but around issues that bring together various field constituents with disparate purposes" and interests (Hoffman, 1999, p. 352). Issues that become important to the interests and objectives of a specific collective define what the field is, making links that may not have previously been made. Hence, an issue-based field is not merely a collection of influential organizations; it is the centre of common channels of dialogue and discussion where competing interests continually negotiate over issue interpretation, and thus the institutions that will guide organizational behaviour (Hoffman, 1999). While not all field constituents will impact on negotiations over issue interpretation, this continual contestation and conflict can result in a process more akin to "institutional war than isomorphic dialogue" (Hoffman, 1999, p. 352) as fields become arenas of power relations in which interpretive struggles are constantly played out among a constellation of actors holding different perspectives underpinned by competing logics (Greenwood and Suddaby, 2006, Lounsbury, 2007, Wooten and Hoffman, 2008). These characteristics render issue-based fields contested and dynamic in contrast to the settled character commonly ascribed to organizational fields (Wooten & Hoffman, 2008)." (O'Sullivan and O'Dwyer 2015)

The concept of 'issue-based-fields' aids the process of revealing greater complexity in field formation and describing and analyzing the dynamics of an organizational field (Hoffmann 1999). The level of structuration i.e. the process of institutional definition is made up of four parts 'an increase in the extent of interaction among organizations in the field: the emerge of sharply defined interorganizational structures of domination and patterns of coalition; an increase in the information load with which organizations in the field must contend; and the development of a mutual awareness among participants in a set of organizations that they are involved in the common enterprise' (DiMaggio and Powell 1991 [1983]: 65).

These can be investigated, making use of the concept of issues-based fields, as these fields can enable and impede SIE initiatives. For instance, an issue-based field represents networks of interactions between actors such as SIE initiatives and more established (often powerful) energy actors who constantly negotiate over appropriate practices relating to common issues at stake (Hoffman, 1999). Most SIE initiatives develop novel processes and contributions e.g. alternative social value creation practices, business and service models, organisational and governance structures, and novel change narratives, often grounded in collaborative processes and collective outcomes.

Institutional work: conceptualization of change within fields

Explanations of change within organizational fields need to be able to conceptualize on the one hand, that institutions constrain actors behaviour and possibilities for changes and on the other hand, that actors can be knowledgeable agents, who are able to influence and change institutions (Leblebici et al. 1991). As argued by Scott (2001: 187), 'in highly institutionalized systems, endogenous change seems almost to contradict the meaning of institution'. Since efforts to change institutions have been

explained either by exogenous forces/ 'disruptive events' (DiMaggio & Powell 1983, Hoffman 1999) or by dominant actors with sufficient resources, such as institutional entrepreneurs (DiMaggio 1988, Garud, Jain and Kumaraswamy, 2002, Garud, Hardy, Maguire 2007).

"... will consider a role for disruptive events in causing a sharp ending to what had become locked-in by institutional inertia (White, 1992). Various referred to as shocks (Fligstein, 1991), jolts (Meyer, 1982) or discontinuities (Lorange, Scott Morton & Ghoshal, 1986), events can take multiple forms, including "milestones (e.g. Earth Day, the Rio Summit); catastrophes (e.g. oil spills, nuclear accidents, toxic fires); and legal/administrative happenings (e.g. parliamentary hearings, trials, release of environmental white papers)" (Hannigan, 1995: 64)." (Hoffmann 1999)

Thus, the question of institutional change has always dealt with the 'paradox of embedded agency' (Holm, 1995; Battilana 2006, Garud et al. 2007). How is it possible that actors shape institutions whilst at the same time being embedded in institutions that are regulative, normative and cultural-cognitively supported? (Möllering 2011).

Rather than purely thinking about shocks, it is possible to take perspective on institutional change where energy transitions are considered to be part of institutionalization processes, which are continuous and will not finish at some point. Drawing on Möllering (2011) and Lawrence and Suddaby (2006) work on institutional work, it is possible to consider neither the notion of 'agency' nor 'embeddness' as dominant within the conceptualization of institutions. They have referred to 'practices as the connecting element between actions and institutions' (Möllering 2011, Lawrence & Suddaby 2006). Institutional changes do not primarily occur through external shocks (x) but also derive from within the field. Lawrence and Suddaby (2006) have defined institutional work as deliberate activities of individuals and/or organizations that aim to create, maintain and transform institutions. The concept of institutional work refers to approaches derived from practice theory (as outlined by Bourdieu 1977, Giddens 1984, Schatzki 2001).

"... the literature on institutional work that is interested in the everyday actions of actors and how they might influence institutionalized rules (Lawrence, Leca, & Zilber, 2013; Lawrence, Suddaby, & Leca, 2009). Practices can be understood - drawing, among others, on Giddens (1984) - as situated patterns of action organized around shared, yet malleable, practical understandings in time space. They are a key element of the institutional work concept as they transcend, by definition, individual action but are nevertheless conceptually rooted in assumptions about agency. Lawrence and Suddaby's (2006:215) definition of institutional work rests on the "the purposive action of individuals and organizations aimed at creating, maintaining and disrupting institutions". (Moellering & Mueller-Seitz 2018)

Drawing on the notion of distributed agency in institutional settings, it is possible to show how actors collectively find new ways of doing things (Moellering and Mueller-Seitz, 2018). 'Thus, adopting a practice perspective on institutions points research and theory towards understanding the knowledgeable, creative and practical work of individual and collective actors aimed at creating, maintaining and disrupting institutions' (Lawrence and Suddaby 2006:12).

"While others have asked which conditions enable or trigger institutional work, i.e., make it more likely (e.g., Hardy & Maguire, 2008; Lawrence, 1999), we propose to study how particular conditions influence how institutional work is performed. In particular, we argue that institutional work is marked, to a greater or lesser extent depending on the field, by the condition of uncertainty understood in the Knightian sense of the actors' inability to know and assess the possible futures (Knight, 1971)." (Moellering & Mueller-Seitz 2018)

SONNET also draws on the notion of institutional work (Lawrence and Suddaby, 2006) to explain deliberate activities of actors that are aimed at creating, maintaining and transforming institutions within issue-based fields and thus referring to practices as the connecting elements between actions and institutions (Moellering and Mueller-Seitz, 2018).

D. What are the gaps in the literature?

“The low-carbon energy transition is a form of socio-technical transition and, as such, it involves profound changes in the institutions that govern society. Despite the acknowledged importance of institutions in shaping the pace and nature of transition, a relatively small proportion of the academic literature on the topic applies institutional theory to the analysis of this transition in a systematic and detailed manner, and these accounts draw mainly on organizational and sociological institutionalism.” (Andrews-Speed 2016)

“While new institutionalism has received considerable attention in recent years to conceptualise socio-technical dynamics in energy transitions, challenges remain in its application to context-specific inter-country comparisons.” (Jehlig et al. 2019)

E. What questions arise for SONNET?

Still need to developed based on conceptual developments

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See also SI-Drive & TRANSIT work on institutions

SOME ADDITIONAL CONCEPTUAL WORK ON INSTITUTIONALISM IN THE LITERATURE (collection of quotes and diagrams)

Analytical framework for comparing energy transitions (Jehlig et al. 2019)

Williamson's three levels of institutions

Research Brief #2b: Research briefing on the possible ways to explore the processes and contributions of SIE-initiatives

Hielscher, Sabine 2020

Reflections on conducting the research briefing

In the proposal, we have outlined concepts that would help us to explore the processes of SIE-initiatives. We said that we would draw on new institutionalism and related concepts e.g. 'institutions' and 'institutional work' - see research briefing on this work to examine SIE-initiatives.

After reading the literature and producing the research brief, I was wondering whether these concepts would 'narrow' our ways of looking at the chosen phenomena of social innovation in energy. For me, explorations into SIE have always felt like a 'David and Goliath' debate.

The EU project Transit has taken a relational perspective on social innovations, examining them as emergent and constructed through the performance of collective practices. A relational perspective provides the resources to open up the diversity, complexities and multiple productions of social innovation practices across the energy system. With this perspective often comes a way of looking at phenomena that presuppose a certain 'flatness' to the world (rather than levels).

I do not propose we move to actor network theory but this quote illustrates the point that I try to make:

"For ANT, the 'social' is not a given but a heterogeneous product laden with the nonhuman - technologies and natures are as much a part of society as humans. Further, the 'social' is not structured in micro, meso and macro layers or spatially arranged into the local and the global (and sometimes the 'glocal'); rather, according to versions of ANT, the social is 'flat', made up of a single layer of associations amongst human and nonhuman entities."

I therefore propose to open up the discussion on how we look at the processes and contributions of SIE-initiatives (at least for a short amount of time):

- STEPS pathways approach (Stirling)
- Directionality (Stirling)

- Innovation democracy (Smith and Stirling)
- Notion of governance beyond the state by Swyngedouw (2005)
- Democratic politics of environmental production (Stirling, Swyngedouw)
- Recent conceptualisation of 'incumbency' by Stirling (2019)
- Flor's work on power and social innovation (not reviewed here)

What are the key insights derived from the literature? - Bullet points

Multiple pathways

“Of all the diverse pathways that are typically viable in any given setting, various self-reinforcing dynamics typically mean that only a few ‘lock-in’. Many others are ‘crowded out’. The strongest pressure ‘close down’ attention around those pathways that are favoured by the most powerful interests. The real challenge, then, is to find ways to ‘open up’ this politics of pathways.” (STEPS website)

Notion of pathways: Pathways are self-reinforcing trajectories of change; subjects and objects are implicated in these pathways as well as those performing it; it implicates social and natural phenomena, agency and structure, discourses, institutions, practices, values, expectations, technologies, intentions, etc.; STEPS interrogates these things themselves and how they relate to each other (Stirling)

How people understand and perform pathways depends on their focus, frames, scope, normativity and perspectives (Stirling)

STEPS approach: Acknowledging and help to acknowledge diverse, multiple and alternative pathways (broadening out assessment and open up knowledge economy: whose knowledge, pathways counts) (Stirling)

“Visions for democracy, lies not merely in ‘opening up’ understandings of the implications of otherwise marginalised perspectives [298]. The aim must also be much more deliberately and directly to critically resist the forces of closure [299]. That such a balanced and reasoned aspiration in academia should.” (Stirling)

Directionality

“This paper argues for greater attention to three inherent attributes of progress: direction, distribution and diversity. These are as relevant to our understandings as to our evaluations of processes of change in knowledges, innovation or development.” (Stirling)

“... wide analytical literatures spanning many disciplines present a wealth of evidence for the ways in which a range of different social, economic and political mechanisms actively shape the directions taken by progress in knowledge, innovation and social development. These processes serve to select and ‘close down’ around a small subset of the potentially technically feasible, economically viable and socially realisable pathways. The result is to prompt the replacement of existing mainstream unitary notions of progress with a more plural model highlighting the property of directionality.” (Stirling)

“Multiple - often radically different - orientations for change are typically feasible and viable. Different directions are favoured under divergent values and interests. Yet mainstream debate over choices between these possible paths tends to revert to polarized discussion around some single, ostensibly unitary, vision for progress. This is as true of Sustainability discourses as it is of preceding and parallel visions of progress. Often, the position is expressed as if there were ‘no alternatives’. The questions asked are thus typically restricted to ‘yes or no?’; ‘how much?’; ‘how fast?’ and ‘who leads?’ If we move instead to more plural understandings of progress, then the quality of debate - and of the ensuing choices - thereby stands to be enriched. Instead of fixating on some single contingently-privileged path, we might ask deeper, more balanced and searching questions about ‘which way?’; ‘what alternatives?’, ‘who says?’ and ‘why?’ This is the essence of a normative, analytic, epistemic, ontological - and consequently intrinsically political - project of ‘pluralising progress’.” (Stirling)

“Directionality refers to the need for more open academic and policy attention to the fact of there being alternative possible orientations for progress. Distribution refers to the imperatives for greater democratic agency, political accountability and social equity in shaping the drivers, benefits and vulnerabilities associated with alternative orientations. Diversity refers to the value of nurturing more plural discourses and cultures around deliberate choice of portfolios of pathways for innovation, sustainable and development - allowing greater variety, dynamism and context-sensitivity in technological and institutional trajectories.” (Stirling)

“How have such vibrant, diverse and enquiring global societies arrived at a situation in which mainstream understandings of progress in knowledge, innovation and development are so consistently impoverished and untenable? How can linear, deterministic ‘sound science’, ‘pro-technology’, ‘way forward’, ‘no alternatives’ rhetorics remain so under-challenged? Why are scalar attributes of progress so widely emphasised in academic analysis with so little interrogation of the crucial property of directionality?” (Stirling)

The crucial difference is, instead, that the characterisation of innovation would then take the form of a vector rather than a scalar quantity. Unlike simple scalar numbers, vectors include the property of direction. In their plurality and relative indeterminacy, the resulting additional parameters of directionality make it far more difficult to assert a single, ostensibly uniquely objective ‘way forward’. This prompts many questions of the

conventional thrust of mainstream economic approaches to technology change mentioned above. For whatever reason, it seems that - despite yielding many crucial insights concerning the directionality of technology and innovation more widely - much economics is in the habit of treating these phenomena overwhelmingly in scalar rather than vector terms. This in turn provides a significant and quite specific reinforcement of the expedient political rhetorics mentioned earlier, which reduce the politics of innovation simply to an impoverished matter of ‘yes or no?’; ‘how much?’; ‘how fast?’ and ‘who leads?’ (Stirling)

Innovation democracy

“Overlooked are the ways these arrangements privilege certain values, interests and positions towards innovation in society, and carry with them a less democratic politics than might be merited by the stakes at hand. We argue innovation is an intensively political activity (Smith et al., 2005).” (Smith and Stirling)

“There is rarely any attempt to try to understand the broader origins, implications and possibilities of grassroots involvement in new, more democratic forms of innovation. Yet this is the most powerful and important feature of grassroots innovation: an insistent opening up of innovation agendas, institutions and practices. (Smith and Stirling)

“The trouble is that democracy is a slippery term. It can mean many contradictory things and is often used quite lazily or cynically. Yet the associated ideas (and practices) themselves are too important to be abandoned - no less for technology than in other areas of social life. In order to have practical progressive meaning, democracy must also be viewed as a process rather than any endpoint. Involving all the many weird and wonderful ways in which power works in society, democratic struggle is about kinds of social relations more than categories of outcome.” (Smith and Stirling)

“So, putting our emphasis as a matter of principle on the interests of the most marginalized groups, we would define democracy in a broad sense - as “access by the least powerful to the capacities for challenging power” (Andy Stirling, 2014b). To put this more specifically in terms of innovation politics, this means: access by the least powerful people and communities to the capacities for challenging the directions of the innovations that affect them.” (Smith and Stirling)

“Two quite distinct meeting points thereby open up between democracy and innovation (including grassroots innovation). The first concerns how innovations might contribute towards enhancing processes of democracy in the above senses. The second concerns the nature and degrees of democracy that are actually realized within the processes of innovation. Rather than being a static endpoint, our analysis points instead to the compelling need for democratic innovation to be seen as an ongoing process - about innovation of all ongoing kinds that serve to improve in any way, access by the least powerful people, to the

capacities for challenging power.” (Smith and Stirling)

Governance beyond the state - Opening up? Innovation democracy?

“International organisations like the EU and the World Bank, as well as leading grassroots movements, have pioneered new and more participatory governance arrangements as a pathway towards greater inclusiveness. Indeed, over the past two decades or so, a range of new and often innovative institutional arrangements has emerged, at a variety of geographical scales. These new institutional ‘fixes’ have begun to challenge traditional state-centred forms of policy-making and have generated new forms of governance-beyond-the state.” (Swyngedouw)

“Governance-beyond-the-state refers in this context to the emergence, proliferation and active encouragement (by the state and international bodies like the European Union or the World Bank) of institutional arrangements of ‘governing’ which give a much greater role in policy-making, administration and implementation to private economic actors on the one hand and to parts of civil society on the other in self-managing what until recently was provided or organized by the national or local state.” (Swyngedouw)

“Our focus will be on the contradictory nature of governance-beyond-the-state and, in particular, on the tension between the stated objective of increasing democracy and citizen’s empowerment on the one hand and their often undemocratic and authoritarian character on the other.” (Swyngedouw)

“When assessing the formal requirements of pluralist democracy against the modes of arrangements of governance-beyond-the-state, the contradictory configurations of these networked associations come to the fore and show the possible perverse effects or, at least, the contradictory character of many of these shifts.” (Swyngedouw)

“Tensions arise between (1) The possibilities and promises of enhanced democratisation through participatory governance versus the actualities of nonrepresentational forms of autocratic elite technocracy. (2) The extension of ‘holder’ participation as partially realised in some new forms of governance versus the consolidation of beyond-the-state arenas of power-based interest intermediation. (3) The improved transparency associated with horizontal networked interdependencies versus the grey accountability of hierarchically articulated and non-formalised and procedurally legitimised, associations of governance.” (Swyngedouw)

“The socially innovative figures of horizontally organized stakeholder arrangements of governance that appear to empower civil society in the face of an apparently overcrowded and ‘excessive’ state, may, in the end, prove to be the Trojan Horse that diffuses and

consolidates the 'market' as the principal institutional form.” (Swyngedouw)

“In a classic ‘radicals dilemma’ [246], ostensible rationales for this, lie in ‘pragmatic’ concerns over how best to effect transformative social and political change [247,248]. Yet - as shown by the early success of the Green movement (like sister movements for emancipation of classes, ethnicities, slaves, workers, colonies, women, young people and diverse sexualities) - there is an irony here [249]. In all these areas, it is in their more distributed and disorderly forms that subaltern social agencies typically affect their most formative influence [250,251]. In their more formally institutionalised forms, it is particular organisations and individuals within these movements that have often become susceptible to treating means as ends - pursuing strategic visibility, organisational positioning and reputational appropriation as proxies for earlier and generally more ambitious aims.” (Stirling)

Democratic politics of environmental production

“Environmental politics is a politics legitimated by a scientific consensus which, in turn, translates into a political consensus. The world is in clear and present danger and urgent, sustained and consensual action is required. This is a politics that ‘legitimizes itself by means of a direct reference to the scientific status of its knowledge’ (Žižek, 2006c: 188) or, in other words, it is a politics reduced to the administration and management of processes whose parameters are defined by consensual socio-scientific knowledges. This reduction of the political to the policing of environmental change, so I shall argue, evacuates if not forecloses the properly political and becomes part and parcel of the consolidation of a postpolitical and postdemocratic polity.” (Swyngedouw)

“Urban socioenvironmental conditions and processes are profoundly political ones and that, consequently, the production of different socio-environmental urban trajectories is a decidedly political process. Considering the properly political is indeed all the more urgent as environmental politics increasingly express a postpolitical consensual naturalization of the political.” (Swyngedouw)

“The aim of this article, in contrast, is to recover the notion of the political and of the political polis from the debris of contemporary obsessions with governing, management, urban polic(y)ing and its associated technologies (Lacoue-Labarthe and Nancy, 1997).” (Swyngedouw)

“... considers whether the political can still be thought of in an environment in which a postpolitical consensual policy arrangement has increasingly reduced the ‘political’ to ‘policing’, to ‘policymaking’, to managerial consensual governing. This reduction of the political to the ‘mode of governing’ is particularly prevalent in environmental practices.” (Swyngedouw)

“Disagreement is allowed, but only with respect to the choice of technologies, the mix of organizational fixes, the detail of the managerial adjustments and the urgency of their timing and implementation. Nature’s apocalyptic future, if unheeded, symbolizes and nurtures the solidification of the postpolitical condition.” (Swyngedouw)

“Rancière’s notion of the political is characterized in terms of division, conflict and polemic (Valentine, 2005). Therefore, ‘democracy always works against the pacification of social disruption, against the management of consensus and “stability” . . . The concern of democracy is not with the formulation of agreement or the preservation of order but with the invention of new and hitherto unauthorised modes of disaggregation, disagreement and disorder’ (Hallward, 2005: 34-5).” (Swyngedouw)

“Democracy is the paradoxical power of those who do not count: the count of the “unaccounted for” ’ (Rancière, 2000b: 124). Therefore, ‘[p]olitics exists wherever the count of parts and parties of society is disturbed by the inscription of a part of those who have no part’ (Rancière, 1998: 123)” (Swyngedouw)

Socio-material incumbency - configuration fields approach

“And the issues are more encompassing than just the ‘socio-technical’ domain of human society and technology. With ‘natural’ materialities also playing crucial roles both as drivers and as implications, the scope extends to wider and deeper ‘socio-material’ dynamics [72-76].” (Stirling)

“The simple point is, then, that even where these neglected alternative pathways are scientifically realistic, technically practicable, economically feasible and socially viable, dynamics of incumbency can prevent them becoming historically realisable [81].” (Stirling)

“Work in related areas has for many decades been giving growing attention to processes and relations implicated in the ‘destabilising’ [120-123], ‘discontinuing’ [124,125], ‘disrupting’ [126,127], ‘unmaking’ [128] (and countervailing ‘maintaining’ [129]) of entrenched directions for change in research and innovation. There are many contrasting emphases.” (Stirling)

“Concept of ‘socio-material incumbency’, as: a ‘multiplexity’ [130,131] of dynamics through which a particular pathway in interacting social, economic, cultural, political, discursive, cognitive, technical and wider material phenomena, is reproduced by - and reinforcing of - associated power gradients. Of course (as always), this definition begs many questions.” (Stirling)

“What is most useful to establish at this initial stage in the discussion, though, is that the framework under which incumbency is interrogated should be as broad-based and unbiased as possible with respect to different perspectives or instances. So, however associated processes are viewed and in whatever contexts, this understanding of ‘socio-material incumbency’ is sufficiently general as to give confidence at minimising undue emphasise or exclusion.” (Stirling)

“So, ‘creative destruction’ of incumbency is often better enabled not so much by specific policies - or even ‘policy mixes [164-167] - as by more diverse general (and deeply political) processes of grassroots mobilisation, collective action, cultural expression and democratic struggle. The analogy here is not with the circumscribed technical orders of a deterministic ‘transition’, understood in terms of structured hierarchies of categorical objects. Instead, what come to the fore are the more openended organic and mutualistic dynamics observable in nature as ‘murmurations’. Here politics and encompassing cultures can be understood in more process-relational ways, with patterns of change sometimes appearing like exquisitely-choreographed flocking behaviours of many animals. When the time is right, it is possible that radical change may thus emerge surprisingly rapidly.” (Stirling)

“... structuration theories remain (for all their abstraction) usefully focused on practical challenges of political action. And it is in the broadly-applicable process-relational terms of structuration theory, that the multiplicities of power asymmetries which constitute gradients of incumbency can be formulated into a quite easily-expressed and readily operational heuristic definition for ‘power’: as different forms and conditions of ‘asymmetrically structuring agency’ [81,253].” (Stirling)

“In particular, the twin components in this conceptualization of power (as relational ‘asymmetries’ in processes of ‘structuring agency’ [81,253]) highlight two specific main aspects of interest: intensity and directionality.” (Stirling)

“The first aspect of the asymmetries referred to in this formulation (of ‘asymmetrically structuring agency’), concerns issues around the intensities of the power gradients themselves. This reflects the repercussions for society and wider environments, of the particular degrees and modalities (and associated relational patterns) in structuring agency that constitute any instance of socio-material incumbency. This is about concentrations of power - the intensity with which a salient assemblage of configuring fields conditions their associated net overall inclination for change at a particular focus (whatever this may be).” (Stirling)

“Second, with regard to processes of ‘structuring agency’ themselves (like the self-reinforcing dynamics summarised in Fig. 1), there are questions over ‘directionality’ - the particular directions of change which these magnitudes of intensities orient [320,321]. What specific kinds of socio-material pathways are favoured (among other possible orientations

for change) by the working of any given instance of incumbency [322]? What other possible forms of wider interlinked social and material change (socio-material pathway) might be suppressed by these patterns [77]? These questions can be quite independent of general issues around power distributions per se. This is because normative judgements over pros and cons of any given power concentration will depend on alignments of interest in subjects and objects. Even a self-styled emancipatory view of incumbency (for instance) might often welcome some specific re-concentration of power, if this favours a particular alternative pathway that happens contingently (or strategically

or tactically) to be preferred by the 'critical' interest in question [323]." (Stirling)

"So, this second aspect of interest goes beyond just the 'scalar intensity' of incumbency around a given socio-material configuration - the simple quantitative magnitude of the associated power concentrations. It additionally introduces their 'vector directionality' [324] - the propensity of incumbent power in this instance to reinforce the orientation of a specific social and political direction for change. Although neglected in much policy-related discussion of innovation and transition [233], this issue of directionality is - at least in political terms - arguably the most important single aspect [43]." (Stirling)

"... intensity and dimensions for orientation in 'asymmetrically structuring agency', distributed across the totality of socio-material configurations, that can be envisioned as 'configuring fields'. And it is the associated processes and relations like... 'lock-in', 'obduracy', 'entrenchment', 'entrapment' etc), that configure the particular directions for socio-material change that actually unfold in any given setting - and which suppress so many others." (Stirling)

"A 'Configuring Fields' approach to socio-material incumbency"

"To have such a broad and balanced way of thinking about power and incumbency is helpful because it must, as has been argued, address asymmetries associated with incumbency that have properties not only of scalar intensity, as concentrations of power, conceivable in a broadly quantitative idiom. Also crucial, it has been shown, are questions over the vector directionality of incumbency, in terms of variously-characterisable - and thus more interpretive - normative orientations in the social and material effects and meanings of these power dynamics. Put in one sentence, then, a pragmatic way to approach what is envisaged, might be in general terms of 'configuring fields' - as 'patterns of propensity with respect to a particular focal socio-material pathway, across the totality of all prehensible socio-material configurations, that serve to foster this specific orientation for change more than others'. (Stirling)

Likewise, 'rhizomic' patterns and flows also subvert rigid differentiations between both hierarchical scales and horizontal categories within these [482,326]. In this light, simply to assume universal neatly-nested category structures with self-evident boundaries (like 'the

regime’), is to commit an error diagnosed by the philosopher Whitehead as ‘the fallacy of misplaced concreteness’ [483,387]. Expressed as asymmetries in processes of structuring agency, then, the resulting patterns of intensity may be envisaged (without any privileging either of structure or agency), to have the effect of orienting directions for socio-material change. So, what has been described amounts simply to the patterns of scalar intensity and vector directionality introduced at the outset, without introducing presumptively concrete discontinuously-bounded and congruent categories like ‘levels’ or ‘regimes’. (Stirling)

Fig. 2. Schematic picture of mutually-defining relations between key concepts in this analysis.

What questions arise for SONNET?

- How to study the processes of SIEs and related initiatives?
- Can we neglect issues of democracy in our investigation?

Key readings/ references

- Direction, Distribution And Diversity! Pluralising Progress In Innovation, Sustainability And Development
- How deep is incumbency? A ‘configuring fields’ approach to redistributing and reorienting power in socio-material change
- Governance Innovation and the Citizen: The Janus Face of Governance-beyond-the-State
- The Antinomies of the Postpolitical City: In Search of a Democratic Politics of Environmental Production
- Innovation, sustainability and democracy: an analysis of grassroots contributions

Research Brief #3: The empirical diversity of social innovation in energy.

Fraaije, M., Wittmayer, J.M. & T. de Geus (2020)

0. Reflections on diversity from the SONNET proposal

Despite the only recent uptake in research and innovation policy, the concept of social innovation has a long history dating back to the early 19th century (e.g. van der Have & Rubalcaba, 2016). This long history adds to the multiplicity of meanings, orientations and uses of social innovation in different public, policy and scientific discourses. Arguably, the most influential definition for social innovation has been coined by BEPA in their seminal report of 2011 on “Empowering people, driving change”, defining social innovations as “new ideas (products, services and models) that simultaneously meet social needs (more effectively than alternatives) and create new social relationships or collaborations. In other words, they are innovations that are not only good for society but also enhance society’s capacity to act.”

Social innovations in the energy sector (SIE) span both supply and demand in different sectors such as mobility, heat, electricity and ICT, and entail the active contributions from consumers, citizens and organizations that go beyond the purchase and adaptation of low carbon technologies. The diversity of such SIE is widely recognized (Seyfang & Haxeltine, 2012; Smith et al., 2016). Attempts to classify and define SIE-initiatives have remained sporadic, despite an increasing interest in social innovations over the last decade (SI-DRIVE, 2016, 2017). There have been a number of attempts to move beyond definitional approaches to characterize SIE. The EU project SIDRIVE, for example, identified three SIE practice fields for renewable energy initiatives: energy collectives (e.g. collective purchasing, energy cooperative, business collectives, co-housing), local production of energy (local production of biofuels, biogas or heat) and providing examples and inspiration (e.g. renewable energy model regions). Coining the term ‘clean energy communities’ (CEC), Gui & MacGill (2018) present three typologies of CECs: centralized (e.g. renewable energy generation projects, energy efficiency, demand-side management, community bulk-buying), distributed (e.g. network of households and businesses that generate and distribute their own energy connected through a controlling entity: virtual power plants (VPP) and peer-to-peer trading) and decentralized (e.g. micro-generation and integrated community energy system (ICES)). Their starting point is the potential future energy system that could be created through SIE. These studies provide a good starting point on how the diversity of SIE could be categorized, but they often focus on infrastructure and technology arrangements and less so on the social dimension of SIE. SONNET therefore further opens up the list of SIE by including power generation, transmission, distribution and consumption as well as other sectors (e.g. mobility, heating and cooling), while at the same time paying dedicated attention to the social dimension of SIE, thereby capturing the full diversity of SIE.

1. Methodology and reflections upon conducting the review

As stated by Hölsgens (2018), “social innovations can be very diverse.” Is the field as diverse as it is stated to be, or can we define certain focal points within SIE literature? And, if so, what are the gaps within SIE literature? This research briefing takes an inductive explorative approach, to find out: what is the diversity of framings of social innovation within an energy context? A very simple literature review was carried out with the search string “social innovation” AND “energy”. This search was run in SCOPUS March 2019, resulting in 69 peer-reviewed articles, out of which 41 were considered relevant after a screening of the abstract. The goal of this approach was to induce the variety of framings of the concept of social innovation within energy transitions. The alternative would have been to compose a search string based on our conceptions of SIE (i.e. “prosumerism”, “cooperatives”, etc). However, to define SIE-initiatives beyond our preconceptions of the concept, an inductive approach was favored over a deductive methodology.

Articles were screened and open-coded in a semi-structured fashion in 8-10 iterations. The main questions investigating during coding were: what type of research subjects are generally studied in the field of SIE, what themes do the authors generally consider while studying SIE initiatives and which energy technologies do they address? The goal was to find the diversity and the gaps within literature.

To find the common research subjects studied in SIE literature, several codes related to the subject upon investigation were clustered into five categories of codes. These were: articles which studied bottom-up initiatives, governance structures, platforms and objects, participatory processes in general or social enterprises. Additionally, 19 social innovation-related and 14 energy-related codes emerged, which were clustered in 8 and 7 groups, respectively.

Lastly, to understand how many authors focus on a specific research subject within the field of SIE, the size of the research field (number of articles) was counted. Furthermore, to find the weight of social innovation as a concept across SIE literature, the term “social innovation” (including its linguistic derivatives) was counted in each article. For more details on the methodology, see “Diversity Brief data analysis.xlsx”, tab: process log.

2. Defining social innovations in the energy transition

The European Commission has coined a definition of social innovation in 2011, stating that social innovations are “new ideas (products, services and models) that simultaneously meet social needs (more effectively than alternatives) and create new social relationships or collaborations. In other words, they are innovations that are not only good for society but also enhance society’s capacity to act” (European Commission, 2011).

Within the field of energy, Hewitt et al (2019), describe SIE as the “reconfiguring of social practices in response to societal challenges, with the aim of improving societal well-being through the engagement of civil-society actors” (Hewitt et al., 2019). Similarly, Hoppe & de Vries (2018) described

that SIEs “contribute to low-carbon energy transition, civic empowerment and social goals, [for] the general well-being of communities.”

Hewitt et al (2019) and Hoppe & de Vries (2018) specifically refer to civic empowerment and civil-society actors. Contrastingly, Hölsgens et al (2018) focuses on social practices in society as whole, stating that SIEs “promote the expectation, generation, distribution and stabilization of alternative everyday practices that can satisfy needs [...] in a less polluting way.” This definition is in line with Soma et al (2019), who refer to SIE as “ways in which changing attitudes, behavior or perceptions are leading to new and improved ways of acting jointly within a group and beyond.”

3. Diversity of social innovation in the energy transition

This section poses the questions: what are the different research subjects of SIE literature, and what is the diversity of social innovation and energy themes within these clusters? A summary of section 3 is presented in table 1 and figure 1.

Table 1. Distribution of social innovation and energy research themes across several research subject clusters (see section 1 for method). *Research subject cluster (horizontal): categories of articles with a similar research focus. Social innovation themes (vertical): the constructed codes for themes (in)directly framed as social innovative qualities. Energy themes (vertical): themes illustrating the energy topic in which the social innovation is placed. General (grey) display: the key reference related to the field, n: the number of articles of the SCOPUS database in this perspective, word count: the relative word count of “social innovation” in the articles of this field (total word count / number of articles in research perspective), as a proxy to indicate the weight of the concept of social innovation.*

		Research subject cluster: article clusters focusing on the same type of initiative					
		Bottom-up initiatives	Governance structures	Platforms and objects	Participatory processes	Social enterprises	Total
Key reference		Docu 2015	Kooij 2018	Hölsgens 2018	Jerneck 2013	Hillman 2018	
GENERAL	n (number of articles)	19	8	4	4	6	41
	Word count “social innovation” / n	9.7	3.8	13.6	10.2	15.3	10.5
SITTHEMES	Increased energy justice	11%	0%	0%	25%	67%	17%
	Novel actors engaged	47%	50%	0%	50%	0%	37%
	Behavior changed	37%	25%	100%	50%	0%	37%
	Inclusive decision making	42%	25%	0%	25%	17%	29%
	New actor relations	21%	50%	25%	0%	17%	24%
	New business model	21%	0%	0%	0%	50%	17%
New governance structure	0%	38%	0%	0%	0%	7%	

ENERGY THEMES	New organizational form	21%	0%	0%	0%	17%	12%
	Energy-efficient housing	32%	50%	50%	75%	17%	39%
	General energy	26%	0%	0%	25%	0%	15%
	Resources (food, materials, etc.)	11%	13%	25%	0%	0%	10%
	Low-carbon mobility	11%	13%	0%	0%	0%	7%
	Smart technology	0%	25%	25%	0%	0%	7%
	Electricity distribution	5%	0%	0%	0%	17%	5%
	Electricity generation	53%	38%	0%	0%	100%	46%

Figure 1. The variety in emphasis on social innovation across five research subject clusters. Colors indicate the various research subject clusters. Number of articles (n): shows the number of articles coded within the same cluster. Average word count per article: a proxy for the weight of social innovation within the field, showing the average number of times “social innovation” was stated throughout the articles. Size of dot: number of articles (n).

3.1 Strong focus on bottom-up initiatives

Inductive open-coding led to five clusters of articles focusing on similar research subjects: bottom-up initiatives, governance structures, platforms and objects, participatory processes and social enterprises (table 1, horizontal). Most SIE literature is focused on bottom-up initiatives (n = 19, figure 1). This focus in line with the civil-society framing of the SIE definitions by Hoppe & de Vries (2018) and Hewitt et al (2019).

Research subjects within this cluster are community energy (Hillman, Axon, & Morrissey, 2018; Maruyama, Nishikido, & Iida, 2007a; Gill Seyfang & Haxeltine, 2012a; Tineke van der Schoor, van Lente, Scholtens, & Peine, 2016), renewable energy cooperatives (Bianchi & Ginelli, 2018; Wierling et al., 2018), grassroots innovation (Gill Seyfang & Haxeltine, 2012a; Vergragt & Brown, 2012; Yalçın-Riollet, Garabuau-Moussaoui, & Szuba, 2014), bottom-up initiatives (Hoelsgens et al., 2018; K Reinsberger & Posch, 2014), civil-society initiatives (Bianchi & Ginelli, 2018; Hatzl, Seebauer, Fleiß, & Posch, 2016; N Magnani & Osti, 2016; G Seyfang & Haxeltine, 2012), renewable energy communities (Dóci, Vasileiadou, & Petersen, 2015), communities (Walker, 2011) or prosumers (T Van Der Schoor, Van Lente, Scholtens, & Peine, 2016).

Bottom-up initiatives are mentioned to be socially innovative, because of their “new social arrangements or business models” (Hatzl et al., 2016), “innovative involvement of civil society in the electricity market” (Natalia Magnani & Osti, 2016), or “civil engagement in the energy transition” (K Reinsberger, Brudermann, Hatzl, Fleiß, & Posch, 2015). In this research perspective, actor engagement is commonly mentioned: “foster[ing] socially innovative engagement practices beyond the purely technological diffusion of innovations” (Nolden, 2013). Often, authors specifically refer to civil society engagement; “bottom-up initiatives are social innovations, which entail civil engagement in energy transition at a local or regional level [...]” (Kathrin Reinsberger, Brudermann, Hatzl, Fleiß, & Posch, 2015).

3.2 Strong focus on behavior change

Several authors perceive social innovation through the lens of individual behavior change (37%, see table 1). This is most apparent within the research subject cluster of platforms and objects, which are described as “online platforms [...] for cross-border lesson study and public classes” (Isoda et al., 2017), a “low carbon toolkit” (Dixon-Declève & Spence-Jackson, 2013), a “business game” for load pricing (Hölsgens, Lübke, & Hasselkuß, 2018) and “platforms to independent producers and designers to sell their products” (Hölsgens et al., 2018). The business game “[allowed] households [to] adjust their consumption practices to the prices” (Hölsgens et al., 2018). Similarly, Dixon-Declève et al (2013) refer to a toolkit as socially innovative because “the results of the toolkit help the schools to create an action plan to reduce their carbon footprint”.

Behavior change is also often mentioned in the context of studying bottom-up initiatives, albeit often more implicitly. In describing a citizen-led solar initiative, Hyytinen et al (2015) state that “the BINSE project can be considered as an example of a social innovation initiative as it aims at changing citizens’ practices and as it targets behavioral routines.” Magnani et al (2016) refer new civil-society led “forms of organized green and ethical consumerism” as a “form of social innovation”. The link between social innovation and behavior is less explicit in Seyfang et al (2010), who study the Transitions Towns and “how social innovations link to macro-level systems change on the one hand and individual-level behavior changes on the other hand”. Even less explicit is Walker (2011), who states that “working through and with communities is typically expected to better embed individual behavior change, as well as generate social innovations and facilitate the consensual deployment of sustainable energy technologies”.

3.3 Little focus on social innovation in articles studying governance structures

Articles may focus on “governance programs” (Karvonen, 2013), “e-governance methods” (Chatfield & Reddick, 2016), non-traditional policy instruments (Ornetzeder, 2001), innovative subsidies (Kooij, Legendijk, & Oteman, 2018), or “government-led national strategies” (Yuan & Zhang, 2014). The weight of social innovation as a concept is relatively low in articles focusing on these governance structures (average word count = 3.8, figure 1). This is in line with the observation that social innovation is often mentioned more ad-hoc, and concrete definitions of SIE are scarce.

Whereas specific mentions of social innovation are scarce, the implied framing of social innovation might be derived from the article. Governance structures are described to lead to “new roles, new responsibilities and new relationships” (de Leeuw & Groenleer, 2018), “changing power relations and social practices” (Tyfield, Ely, & Geall, 2015), or “facilitate engagement between occupants, housing providers, community groups, local authorities and construction professionals” (Karvonen, 2013).

3.4 Lack of explicit framings of social innovation

The qualities which render the initiative or its outcomes as socially innovative are often not explicitly described. These implicit framings mainly occur in articles that refer to a socially innovative effect of a specific initiative. For example, Karvonen (2013) states that “domestic retrofit programs [...] promote social innovation”, leaving the understanding of what it is that is being promoted up for the interpretation of the reader. The exception is provided by Hyytinen (2015), stating that “Bottom-up grassroots activities are described as an “engine of social innovations”, promoting “responsible citizenship” (Hyytinen & Toivonen, 2015).

Contrastingly, explicit framings are prevalent in articles that view the organizational form, business model, or policy of the initiative itself as the social innovation (de Leeuw & Groenleer, 2018; Goyal, Sergi, & Kapoor, 2017; Kooij et al., 2018; Kathrin Reinsberger et al., 2015). For example, Kooij (2018) “studies the emergence and evolution of the PCR [subsidy scheme] as an example of a successful social innovation in the energy transition.” Additionally, de Leeuw & Goenleer (2018) state that “regional governance can be seen as an important social innovation in itself”. In the same way, Reinsberger et al (2015) posits that “bottom-up initiatives are social innovations, which entail civil engagement in energy transition at a local or regional level [...]”. Lastly, Goyal et al. (2017) state that “social enterprise operations [are] a form of social innovation”.

3.5 Photovoltaics stimulate energy justice through social enterprises

Several articles study social enterprises (Goyal et al., 2017; Hillman et al., 2018; Ralitsa Hiteva & Sovacool, 2017; Warnecke & Houndonougbo, 2016), “not for profit companies” or “business models for inclusive sustainable growth” (Ralitsa Hiteva & Sovacool, 2017; Soma, van den Burg, Selnes, & van der Heide, 2019).

Social enterprises are often involved in photovoltaics (Hillman et al., 2018). This technology might be referred to as “solar energy” (Goyal et al., 2017), “solar home system kits” and “pico-solar systems” (Warnecke & Houndonougbo, 2016). Here, the technology is instrumental in embedding the concept of energy justice within society, i.e. through “rural electrification” (Warnecke & Houndonougbo, 2016), “offering low cost energy (tariffs) to households” (R Hiteva & Sovacool, 2017), “embedding energy justice concepts in business models for energy provision” (Hillman et al., 2018) and “providing energy [...] to vulnerable consumers [...] and tackling fuel poverty” (Ralitsa Hiteva & Sovacool, 2017).

3.6 Strong focus on electricity generation

Electricity generation through wind and photovoltaic technology is the most dominant energy theme in SIE literature. The theme mainly plays a large role in social enterprises and bottom-up initiatives. Bottom-up initiatives may generate their own electricity to “cover their own energy needs” (Dóci et al., 2015), or to “reinvest a share of the earning in the community” (R Hiteva & Sovacool, 2017). This is either through wind power (R Hiteva & Sovacool, 2017; Maruyama, Nishikido, & Iida, 2007b; Nolden, 2013), or photovoltaics (Hölsgens et al., 2018; Kathrin Reinsberger et al., 2015). Social enterprises focus mostly on photovoltaics (Goyal et al., 2017; Hillman et al., 2018; Ralitsa Hiteva & Sovacool, 2017; Warnecke & Houndonoubo, 2016) and hydropower (Hillman et al., 2018).

3.7 Strong focus on energy-efficient housing

Literature focuses strongly on energy efficiency in the built environment. The topic is handled generally, i.e. by studying “Green House Gas reduction in the built environment” (Dixson-Declève & Spence-Jackson, 2013), “reduced household energy usage” (Hiteva, 2017), projects that “support households to save energy” (Hölsgens et al., 2018), and “sufficiency-optimised homes” (Lorek & Spangenberg, 2019). Alternatively, studies may focus on specific programs such as “housing retrofit programs” (Karvonen, 2013), or technologies such as “flue-piped stoves that save energy” (Jerneck & Olsson, 2013)

4. What are the gaps?

Social innovation is often mentioned offhandedly in SIE literature, lacking a description of the socially innovative qualities. In this way, it is often unclear as to whether the social innovative aspects are captured in the practices of the initiative itself (i.e. its organizational form), or their aspired goals (i.e. energy poverty reduction). Moreover, literature often lacks a comparison to the current dominant practice, thereby lacking a description of the innovative quality of the practice discussed.

Moreover, while social innovations in energy are said to be very diverse (Hölsgens et al., 2018), the focus of literature is on some aspects rather than others. For example, SIE is mainly explored through the perspective of bottom-up civil-society initiatives ($n = 19$), while governance structures are less discussed ($n = 8$). Furthermore, SIE literature mostly refers to the importance of actor engagement (37%) or behavior change (37%), while new governance structures (7%), new organizational forms (12%) and battling energy poverty (17%) are less popular topics (table 1, ‘total’ row). In terms of the energy contexts, there seems to be a large focus on energy usage in housing (39%) and electricity generation (46%), whereas smart technology (7%) and electricity distribution (5%) are less often discussed (table 1, ‘total’ row).

Lastly, whereas the term innovation only implies “novel”, current SIE literature has a predominantly positive framing of SIEs, for example by reducing energy poverty (17%), leading to reduced energy usage (37%) or leading to inclusive decision making processes (29%) (table 1, ‘total’ row).

5. What questions arise for SONNET?

Literature leaves space for unpacking the concept of social innovation, and would benefit from a solid conceptual understanding of the qualities which render a practice socially innovative within the energy context, as compared to the current dominant energy practice.

Moreover, SONNET could increase the breadth of the understanding of SIEs, by focusing on topics which have previously been under addressed in literature, such as social innovations as new governance structures and organizational forms (table 1). In terms of energy contexts, the realm of smart technology, storage and electricity distribution could possibly widen the research field, which is currently predominantly focused on issues of electricity generation and housing efficiency.

Lastly, the positive framing of the term “innovation” in SIE literature creates the question: which novel social practices have a negative effect on the transition towards a low-carbon energy system?

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Research Brief #4: Defining the success of social innovation in energy.

Winzer, C., Schmid, B., Dzukowski, T. & D. Wemyss (2019)

Aim of the briefing to define evaluation schemes, and SIE and EU goals relevant for SONNET and identify existing themes and gaps in the current literature grounded on SONNET Mendeley literature database.

From proposal- The aim of WP 6 is to evaluate and assess the success of SIE initiatives (analysed in WP 3) to making energy more secure, sustainable, competitive, and affordable and to increase competitiveness and preserve livelihoods through their diverse socio-political, socio-cultural and socio-economic contributions (e.g. novel business model, governance arrangements or narratives).

Task 6.1 EU and SIE goal alignment analysis (M6-M25) (16%)

Lead: ZHAW, co-lead: SPRU, further involvement: all partners.

The goal alignment mapping to determine successful SIE focuses on European Energy Union objectives that is compared to the goals and aims of SIE-initiatives. Starting with the goals identified in the literature review (T1.1 including policy documents) a first draft of a goal alignment map is developed for the 30 SIE-initiatives studied in WP3 and discussed at a partner workshop (M8.3). Goals are categorised from a multi-bottom line perspective reflecting that SIE-initiatives may not be only profit driven. A final version of the goal alignment map is produced after the specific goals of the 30 SIE-initiatives have been collected in WP3 (T3.2). By including these specific SIE goals in the map the alignment of SIE goals and EU Energy Union objectives, as well as goal setting and alignment patterns can be identified across different SIE types and countries across Europe (D6.1).

Task 6.2 Develop an evaluation scheme for SIE success (M11-17) (38%)

Lead: ZHAW, co-lead: SPRU, further involvement: all partners.

An evaluation scheme is developed (M6.1) which includes SMART indicators (i.e. specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and timely) for the goals identified in D6.1, along with a rating scale defining the level of completion and success. Examples of direct indicators are changes in

- Secure: prosumption level, renewable connections, energy savings;
- Sustainable: electricity consumption, reduction of CO₂ and other pollutants, engagement level, % of female social innovators, the impact on the acceptance for the energy transition;
- Competitive: taking a global perspective towards reskilling and enhancing specifically Europe's competitiveness
- Affordable: re-skilling of energy workers, creation of local jobs, value of local generation remains in the local community.

Based on existing frameworks from the literature the evaluation scheme also includes additional benefits (indirect indicators), as outcomes may have interaction, side or spill-over effects, and therefore potential multiple benefits. For example, an energy co-operative may have been founded to take advantage of wholesale purchase pricing (direct indicator: electricity prices for cooperative members), and additionally has the opportunity to better manage financial and natural resources (side effect -> indirect indicator: use of local natural resources), as well as potentially increasing social justice concerning energy poverty (improving livelihoods as spill-over effect -> indirect indicator: local income). A draft version of the evaluation scheme (containing the goals, indicator

metric, and scales) is reviewed at a partner workshop (M8.5), thereby gathering feedback from members of the advisory board as well as academic and city partners. In addition, 2-3 further policy and SIE experts are invited to join this review meeting.

Task 6.3 Apply the evaluation scheme for SIE success (M17-27) (46%)

Lead: ZHAW, co-lead: SPRU, further involvement: all partners.

The refined evaluation scheme is applied to the 30 SIE-initiatives, which means that the relevant indicators from the evaluation scheme are selected for each SIE (D6.3). Data collection for the relevant indicators will be facilitated by the provision of contact details of suitable experts within the 30 SIE-initiatives analysed in WP3 (T3.2), who are interviewed regarding available data. This data collection for all 30 SIE-initiatives are further supplemented by additional data sources, such as official local, regional, national and European statistics and databases. The gathered data is used to evaluate and characterise the success of the different SIE types in six different countries, thereby allowing for cross-case and cross-country comparisons. This evaluation allows for a better understanding of what are successful examples of SIE and how they contribute to EU energy policy objectives of achieving more secure, sustainable, competitive, and affordable energy systems, while preserving livelihoods and improving competitiveness.

Reflections on conducting the review

- Most studies look at the conditions that lead to success ex-post, but do not provide a framework for analysis.
- Some theoretical defined frameworks emerged in the literature review, but I did not follow-up on their disciplinary origins
- A few papers do address achievement of local and EU energy goals (see policy assessment section)
- Some papers actively distinguish between initiative goals and participant's motivations. These do not necessarily have to match. (Horiuchi, 2018; Peters, Fudge, High-Pipper, Carragher, & Hoffman, 2018; Sloot, Jans, & Steg, 2018)

What do we know from the literature? (Sonnet July 2019 Mendeley database. Keywords: success)

Goal definition

Typologies

- Prosumer (Reid & Ellsworth-Krebs, 2017) and benefits (Karjalainen & Ahvenniemi, 2019)
- Community-based sustainability initiatives strive to challenge and improve policy makers. (Celata & Coletti, 2019)
- Socio-ecological-technical systems framework for investment motivations of community energy. (Holstenkamp & Kahla, 2016)

- Typologies of community renewable energy projects (Hicks & Ison, 2018; Klein & Coffey, 2016; Seyfang, Park, & Smith, 2013). Renewable energy cooperatives in Spain (Heras-Saizarbitoria, Saez, Allur, & Morandeira, 2018)

Facets

- Long term continuity (Horiuchi, 2018)
- Diversity of motivations (Bauwens, 2016)
- Energy justice (Forman, 2017)

Evaluation frameworks

Technology assessments

- GIS method to assess community energy production potential (solar, wind, hydro, bio). Further studies planned to discuss community acceptability and resource resilience (Gormally, Whyatt, Timmis, & Pooley, 2012)
- CO2 reduction (Feng, Tian, Li, & Xu, 2017)
- Demand side response evaluation in households (Jones, Taylor, Kipp, & Knowles, 2010)

Social assessments

- Ecological citizenship framework: the extent to which each community's energy project displays the characteristics of ecological citizenship, in terms of how their collectivity is organized, articulated and shaped the future goals and vision (Islar & Busch, 2016). Results-community energy development prioritises community development (economic) rather than societal goals (climate change).
- Local impacts such as empowerment, energy security, social capital, low carbon effectiveness (Berka & Creamer, 2018; Celata & Sanna, 2019)
- Impact of an actor network (Maruyama, Nishikido, & Iida, 2007; van der Waal, van der Windt, van Oost, & J, 2018)
- Industrial transition movements (Hess, 2018)
- Strategic action fields (Fuchs, 2016)

Economic assessment

- Model of policy impacts on community renewables (Lakshmi & Tilley, 2019)
- Financial incentives for participation (Curtin, McInerney, & Johannsdottir, 2018)
- Macroeconomic impact of prosumers in DE (Flaute, Großmann, Lutz, & Nieters, 2017)

Policy assessment

- Goal achievement correlated with policy environment (Celata & Coletti, 2019)
- Role of energy cooperatives in energy transition (Wierling et al., 2018)
- Achievement of broader goals (Sifakis, Savvakis, Daras, & Tsoutsos, 2019)
- Achievement of EU goals (Stuart Wabe, 1988)
- Bottom up contributions in DE (Akizu et al., 2018)

Perceived success

- Solar communities in US (Peters et al., 2018)
- Community-owned renewable projects in Indonesia (Guerreiro & Botetzagias, 2018)

Literature Review methodology:

- Gathering main categories by screening “Mapping of social innovations...” on OneDrive and by checking key literature: (Celata, F., & Sanna, V. S., 2019; G., Park, J. J., & Smith, A., 2013)
- Determining the goals of SIE in these categories regarding three aspects: Goals of SIE, Motivation of members/citizens and suggestions of paper
- Detailed overview of what paper contains which goal: https://zhaw-my.sharepoint.com/:x:/g/personal/betz_zhaw_ch/Eegh6_va6_JOvcxDCj3N3ZQB586K-wGb4XreXdlzUCIMMw?e=shMdhK
-

G. What are the gaps in the literature?

- Not clear if technology choice plays a role. Most studies refer to renewable energy technologies all together (combining hydro, wind, solar and bio)

H. What questions arise for SONNET?

- How to reconcile the diversity of the SIE under one evaluation framework?

- EU and SIE goals can be faceted to address specific issues
- Perceived SIE success likely important to analyse in WP3

Key readings (From July 2019 Mendeley folder. Some themes in parentheses)

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- Berka, A. L., & Creamer, E. (2018). Taking stock of the local impacts of community owned renewable energy: A review and research agenda. *RENEWABLE & SUSTAINABLE ENERGY REVIEWS*, 82(3), 3400–3419. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.10.050> (local assessment)
- Wierling, A., Schwanitz, V. J., Zeiss, J. P., Bout, C., Candelise, C., Gilcrease, W., ... Sterling. (2018). Statistical Evidence on the Role of Energy Cooperatives for the Energy Transition in European Countries. *SUSTAINABILITY*, 10(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10093339> (policy assessment)
- Sifakis, N., Savvakis, N., Daras, T., & Tsoutsos, T. (2019). Analysis of the Energy Consumption Behavior of European RES Cooperative Members. *ENERGIES*, 12(6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12060970> (broader goal achievement)
- Akizu, O., Bueno, G., Barcena, I., Kurt, E., Topaloglu, N., & Manuel Lopez-Guede, J. (2018). Contributions of Bottom-Up Energy Transitions in Germany: A Case Study Analysis. *ENERGIES*, 11(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11040849> (broader goal alignment)
- Stuart Wabe, J. (1988). The weak links in community energy policy. *Energy Policy*, 16(3), 305–307. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0301-4215\(88\)90154-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0301-4215(88)90154-1) (policy assessment)

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Research Brief #5: Insights on the future potentials of social innovations in energy.

Marie-Charlotte Guetlein, Joachim Schleich (2019)

I. Short description

The briefing reviews the existent literature relevant for the assessment of the future potential of SIE in SONNET WP5. This includes an assessment of methods proposed in the literature to assess future potential of SIE. The briefing further identifies gaps in the literature and resulting questions arising for SONNET WP5.

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J. Reflections on conducting the review

In SONNET WP5, three large-scale citizen surveys are conducted to generate a comprehensive understanding of the future potential of selected types of SIE in terms of their scope and diffusion within the energy system. To do so, the surveys include stated preferences discrete choice experiments (SPDCE) on up to four types of SIE. The analysis of the SPDCE allows estimating the market shares and hence potential of particular services and/or products offered through the SIE, thereby identifying which type of SIE is most likely to be successful. This analysis further provides evidence on the implications for the design of SIE-initiatives, for companies' business models, as well as for future policy interventions.

The literature review is guided by the following questions:

- Has future potential of SIE been assessed in the literature using SPDCE? What type of SIE? How were SIE characterized (attributes, drivers, barriers, trade-offs)? What were the results?
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- What diffusion issues have been identified in the literature? Which SIE characteristics – if any – have been identified as drivers/barriers to diffusion?
-
- Is there evidence on the effects of individual and household characteristics on the acceptance of SIE or specific services and/or products offered through SIE?

K. What do we know from the literature?

There is a large body of literature on SPDCE, mainly in transportation, marketing, environmental economics, energy economics and health economics. This also includes literature on the evaluation of future potential of diverse services and products. Applications to SIE are rare, however.

Azarova et al. (2019) use data from a SPDCE in Germany, Austria, Italy and Switzerland to analyze acceptance of renewable energy communities. The authors discuss how acceptance (and hence future potential) of energy communities depends on technologies used, political support and

individual characteristics. They find that the inclusion of photovoltaics or power-to-gas in local energy communities leads to a significant increase in acceptance within the population. Moreover, Italian respondents' acceptance of energy infrastructure is influenced by EU and national governmental bodies, while Swiss respondents react to local politicians' opinions. Age, gender, education and number of children are also found to have an effect of acceptance of renewable energy systems.

Knoefel et al. (2018) use a SPDCE in Germany to evaluate household respondents' willingness to pay (WTP) for co-determination rights, transparent pricing, as well as electricity utilities' profit distribution. All three aspects are found to increase WTP for electricity. Based on their results, the authors suggest that a "democratic governance" label could help citizen-led projects in renewable energy gain market shares.

Salm et al. (2016) conduct a SPDCE with retail investors in Germany, who stated an interest in investing in community-based renewable energy projects. While return on investment was found to be the most crucial factor for their investment choices, the minimum holding period and the issuer of the investment offerings (i.e. municipality, energy cooperative, or financial institution) were found to be important as well. Moreover, respondents stated a preference for solar power compared to wind and small hydropower. The authors also identified a group of "local patriots" with stronger preference for local projects compared to "yield investors" whose choices are more strongly driven by rate of return.

Other existing choice experiments that could be of interest in the context of SONNET WP5 look at

- consumer preferences for different sources of renewable energy and auto-consumption (Borchers et al., 2007)
- energy mix and location of electricity generation (Gracia et al., 2012)
- energy mix, provider, and location of electricity generation (Kaenzig et al. 2013)
- characteristics of wind parcs and citizen involvement in the planning process (Dimitropoulos and Kontoleon, 2009)
- PV systems, financial and environmental benefits, as well as development of energy prices, energy policies and social norms (Islam and Meade, 2013)
- PV systems and financial incentives (subsidies, low-interest loans) (Jeong, 2013)

Looking beyond SPDCE, various authors (see examples below) have identified different barriers and drivers for SIE and studied the effects of individual and household characteristics on acceptance of and participation in SIE initiatives. While this literature is typically not looking at expected market shares of SIE, it will help guide the choice of attributes in the SPDCE conducted in WP5 as well as the selection of survey questions complementing the SPDCE.

- Kalkbrenner and Roosen (2016) use survey data to study citizen participation in community-based renewable energy projects. Their results show that "willingness to volunteer is higher than willingness to invest financial resources". In terms of future potential, this indicates that requiring financial investments by citizens can be an important barrier. Besides, the authors observe that trust, social norms, environmental concern and higher income have positive effects citizen's willingness to volunteer and/or invest.

- Surveying US residents, Peters et al. (2018) analyze challenges and opportunities for community-driven solar energy projects. The authors highlight that the local and community character of projects combined with environmental and/or personal economic benefits drives citizen participation.
- Reid and Ellsworth-Krebs (2017) look at UK online discussion forums to gain insights on drivers for household solar thermal panels. They observe a high demand for household-specific advice and solutions that match individual (current and expected future) uses. Besides financial reasons, modernization and comfort appear to be key factors.
- Palm and Eriksson (2018) focus on informational barriers preventing household adoption of PVs.
- Kotilainen and Saari (2018) find that "secure data and access to information are important to consumers". Based on a survey conducted in five European countries they further observe that regulatory barriers hinder consumer participation (e.g. in energy trading) across countries.
- Micheals and Parag (2016) use a household survey in Israel to study perception on "prosuming services" such as demand reduction, load shifting, or energy storage technologies and identified a number of barriers to these services, including health and privacy concerns, trust, social norms, and high upfront costs.
- Kowalska-Pyzalska (2018) studies the relation between socio-economic characteristics as well as environmental attitudes and willingness to pay for green electricity among Polish consumers.
- Also in Poland, Ropuszynska-Surma et al. (2018) observe that financial barriers are the most important factor preventing households from installing microgeneration technologies.

Keywords (barriers/drivers):

- | | |
|-----------------------|----------------------|
| - social norms | - environmental |
| - trust | benefits/environe |
| - democratic | ntal attitude |
| governance | - upfront costs |
| - participation | - economic/financial |
| - transparency | benefits |
| - political support | - local/community |
| - health concerns | character of |
| - privacy concerns | projects |
| - information (access | - income |
| to/form/lack | - age, gender, |
| of/source of/etc.) | number of children, |
| - advice | education |
| - regulatory barriers | |
| - comfort | |
| - modernization | |

L. What are the gaps in the literature?

- - few choice experiments in the area of social innovation in energy; to our knowledge none in France or Poland. Existing ones address future potential of SIE only indirectly (e.g. no market shares are calculated). This also implies that potential is typically not quantified.
 - few cross-country studies
 - business model implications (?)

M. What questions arise for SONNET?

- How can SPDCE methods that are used in other contexts be applied to evaluate the potential of particular services and/or products offered through SIE? What are the constraints or limitations?
- What are the constraints or limitations in applying SPDCE to evaluate future potential (in general and for SIE in particular)?

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Research Brief #6: Research brief on socio-cultural aspects of social innovation in energy - a first draft

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January 2020

1. Reflections on conducting the literature review of the topic: challenges/ opportunities

Our approach

- The SONNET Mendeley database contains 172 articles tagged with 'socio-cultural'. We pragmatically divided the articles (plus an additional one) along several themes that we had defined to be linked to the 'socio-cultural' theme during our Karlsruhe meeting. Based on this, each of us took on specific topics and reviewed the corresponding articles.
- This review is not finished yet, out of 173 article abstracts, we have covered 123 articles leaving another 50 to be analysed in a next round. We covered the following topics: Autonomy (10), Behaviour (8), Gender (2), Roles (7), Social acceptance (14), Social relations (14) and parts of Narratives (28) and a residual 'Other' category (73). We still miss Values (15).
- Several articles were removed from further analysis because they did not concern scientific resources or socio-cultural phenomena.
 - o Deleted: (Acosta et al., 2018; Burns & Midttun, 1986; Cohen, Pearlmutter, & Schwartz, 2010; Dill, McNeil, & Howland, 2019; Frantzeskaki, Avelino, & Loorbach, 2013; Fuentes González, Sauma, & van der Weijde, 2019; Girvitz & Lipp, 2005; Hindmarsh & Matthews, 2008; Kostevsek, Cizelj, Petek, & Pivec, 2013; Kurbatova, 2018; Lemon, Pollitt, & Steer, 2015; Markantoni & Aitken, 2016; McCabe, Pojani, & van Groenou, 2018; Mignon & Rüdinger, 2016; Palm & Eriksson, 2018)(Mignon & Rüdinger, 2016)
- We added additional articles about 'gender' to the review.
- We scanned this literature to understand more in general what is pulled together under 'socio-cultural' considerations related to energy.

2. What are the key insights derived from the literature?

2.1. Autonomy and Autarchy

Autonomy and autarchy are keywords that are often present in the debate around the energy transition. They relate to the idea that certain units - social, geographical - became (more) independent of the (usually national) energy system. **Technological enablers** usually include small-scale generation units for electricity.

The autarchy discussion also has a **psychological** dimension of being less dependent and therefore more autonomous which can be a driver towards certain activities for some groups or individuals. It has also a national dimension as a policy goal which, however, in a paper by (Michaels & Parag, 2016) did not increase support for prosuming technologies and applications.

- Identified by (Bomberg & McEwen, 2012) as a symbolic resource for **mobilization** in Scottish community energy groups: „desire for strong, self reliant communities“
- Autonomy as a potential **attribute of participatory processes** of regional energy transitions (Komendantova, Riegler, & Neumueller, 2018)
- Energy autarchy as “...a situation in which the energy services used for sustaining local consumption, local production and the export of goods and services are derived from locally renewable energy resources.” which requires a socio-structural-technical transformation in the region that wants to achieve autarchy (Müller, Stämpfli, Dold, & Hammer, 2011); Besides the description of the concept and the benefits its implementation brings, this article provides a process for implementation, and some examples from Austria, Germany and Switzerland.
- Analysis of **partial autarchy** in an eco-community in contrast to higher level strategies through a **spatio-temporal** lens on a socio-technical process (Sareen, Baillie, & Kleinwachter, 2018)
- A critical discussion of “recent turns in the localist discourse in the UK which emphasise self-reliant communities and envisage a diminished role for the state” is provided by (Catney et al., 2014)
- (Schumacher, Krones, McKenna, & Schultmann, 2019) “explore for the first time how **public acceptance** is linked with community energy and energy autonomy”
- The paper “connects alternative approaches towards novel, sustainable, and more **democratic forms** of energy provision [...] The typology encompasses alternative approaches to energy provision and governance [...] including instances of local autonomy in decentralised systems [...]” (Becker & Naumann, 2017)
- A further term used is **self-sufficiency** (Akizu et al., 2018) - the case study based paper shows how initiatives reach the goals of reducing primary energy consumption, reducing residential electricity and heat consumption and increase the use of renewable energy such that attaining self-sufficiency is possible

2.2. Social acceptance

A **definition** from Upham et al. (2015) describes (social) acceptance as “a favourable or positive response (including attitude, intention, behaviour and – where appropriate – use) relating to a proposed or in situ technology or socio-technical system, by members of a given social unit (country or region, community or town and household, organisation)”. It draws on the regularly cited definition by Wüstenhagen (2007) who differentiates socio-political, local and market acceptance as facets of acceptance.

Socio-political acceptance refers to the general societal climate towards a technology or innovation within a society, i.e. it relates to typical discussions about a topic or social desirable opinion. *Community acceptance* is a concept that is most relevant for siting decisions and refers to the attitudes and behaviours exhibited by neighbours of installations or others somehow affected by an innovation or technology without actually using it. *Market acceptance* finally refers to the acceptance of a technology that is manifested by market

actors, i.e. supply and demand side as well as intermediate actors like installers, consultants etc. All of these facets of social acceptance are potentially relevant for SIE.

- (Büscher & Sumpf, 2015) look into the role of **trust and distrust** and (McComas, Stedman, & Hart, 2011) into **procedural fairness** - bot key constructs from social acceptance research.
- a **research agenda** was provided by (Wolsink, 2012) strengthening also the **institutional** perspective in addition to socio-psychological topics
- A review for small scale energy systems in local neighbourhoods is provided by (T. von Wirth, Gislason, & Seidl, 2018): Their “findings indicate that local coownership and awareness of local benefits tend to improve the acceptance”; they also emphasise, in line with (Wolsink, 2012), the relevance of the **institutional** / governance perspective
- a large stream of literature has emerged in the last ten years relating energy transitions and the **spatial dimension** and what the spatial dimension means for people; as an exemplary publication we refer to (Suesser et al., 2017)
- The most important factors influencing the acceptance of wind energy projects, are sound levels in the house, the distance of the turbine and participation opportunities. Residents in Germany preferred **information participation over financial participation** (Langer, Decker, & Menrad, 2017)
- The acceptance of renewable energy in Poland was found to be linked to income, education, pro-environmental attitudes, knowledge, and social influence. Authors advice to implement “ stable legal regulations, clear procedures, subsidies, social campaigns, and educational trainings” (Kowalska-Pyzalska, 2018)
- In a study on energy governance in the EU, researchers found that “engagement in energy governance is affected by path-dependence [...] and determined by dissatisfaction with policy decisions taken at that level” (Tosun, Zoeckler, & Rilling, 2019)
- use and acceptance of distributed energy storage (DES) technologies hinges on **public perception**; these perceptions are considered as part of a broader renewable energy landscape (culture); acceptance and adoption of DES at household/community level are shaped by forms of energy consumption; costs; expectations of family members; previous experiences; perceptions of government and the municipal authority; and expectations about the technologies (using Energy Cultures Framework for analysis) (Ambrosio-Albala, Upham, & Bale, 2019)

Trust

- Trust is important for cooperation within community energy (Kalkbrenner & Roosen, 2016; Polach, Kunze, Maass, & Grundmann, 2015; Seyfang, Park, & Smith, 2013; Walker, Devine-Wright, Hunter, High, & Evans, 2010; Wiersma & Devine-Wright, 2014)
 - o Trust is an important **driver** of community energy (Walker et al., 2010)
 - o Community renewable energy is benefitted by **social capital** such as “trust among all actors based on transparency” (Polach et al., 2015)
 - o “Social norms, trust, environmental concern and community identity are important **determinants of willingness** to participate” in community energy projects (Kalkbrenner & Roosen, 2016)
 - o **Intermediary organisations** can “spread some types of learning necessary for diffusion”, but it is not enough, as “tacit knowledge, trust and confidence are essential to these projects’

- success” and these are difficult to extrapolate to novel contexts through intermediaries (Seyfang et al., 2013)
- **Mistrust** of energy companies is a driver of community energy (Lehtonen & de Carlo, 2019; Wiersma & Devine-Wright, 2014), whereas local non-profits are “benefitted by trust of local residents” (Wiersma & Devine-Wright, 2014)
 - Trust is also dependent on **long-time engagement** of community residents (Wiersma & Devine-Wright, 2014)
 - Public acceptance of hydrogen is supported by **trust of experts**: Citizen panels for new hydrogen technologies urge for ‘critical trust’ of experts (Flynn, Ricci, & Bellaby, 2013)
 - The role of the emotions of **insecurity/uncertainty** in the ambition to mitigate consequences of the Chernobyl disaster by West German initiatives in Belarus (and also relates it to New Social Movement) (Arndt, 2010)
 - Strategies to enable to cope experimentally with **unforeseen risks** in developing geothermal heating (environmental impacts, technical feasibility, ...) and those cope with uncertainties that arise in ongoing energy transitions (Bleicher & Gross, 2016)

Opposition

- There is a “social gap” between positive general attitudes toward renewable energy development and local resistance to actual proposals.” (Giordono, Boudet, Karmazina, Taylor, & Steel, 2018)
- Opposition stems from “ proximity to protected areas, political opportunity, and opponents’ framing of the risks posed by wind development are important factors in driving community resistance.” (Giordono et al., 2018)
- Lack of engagement with wind projects in Ontario, Canada, explains the resistance to wind projects (Songsore, Buzzelli, & Baxter, 2018).
- Community acceptance focus in Australian regulation does not lead to higher acceptance. Causes are found to be “problematic reliance on procedural compliance in assessing wind farm consultation, domination by vested interests, and reduced expertise in community engagement at the time it is needed most.” (Howard, 2015)

2.3. Participation, engagement and procedural fairness

Several studies evolve around participation principles in the energy transition, often referring to community acceptance as a target variable. There is certainly a broader literature on this (participation and/or community energy), however, in this brief we only touch upon a few recent studies in this field.

The findings reviewed include:

- the relevance of **design features** enabling collective attention and action (Bourazeri & Pitt, 2018),
- **attributes of members** of community energy activities (Bauwens & Devine-Wright, 2018),
- **factors** that are likely to foster citizen and community participation, focusing on wind power cooperatives in Denmark, Germany, Belgium and the UK (Bauwens, Gotchev, & Holstenkamp, 2016)

- an approach focusing on **human needs** is presented by (Centgraf, 2018)
- the interplay between citizen engagement and **local acceptance** (Gormally, Pooley, Whyatt, & Timmis, 2014)
- **types of stakeholder influence** clustered around the dimensions macro, intercommunity and intracommunity (Ruggiero, Onkila, & Kuittinen, 2014); furthermore they point to “the importance of two stakeholder groups: intermediary organizations and local champions. These were groups whose positive influence was crucial in the implementation phase [...]”
- diverse forms of participation in energy systems transitions have been captured through an ‘**ecologies of participation**’ approach; some of these forms are more ‘prevalent, legitimate and ‘central’ than others (there are thus systemic inequalities of participation and inclusion in socio-technical change): particularly behaviour change and forms of public elicitation to gain social acceptance; high importance of interrelations and mutual influence between collective practices of participation (Chilvers, Pallett, & Hargreaves, 2018)
- Focus on **social scale** through which to achieve optimum forms of local participation and ownership (in contrast to reverse-engineered solutions oriented approaches looking for financial and technical scalability) exploring interaction between three forms of energy literacy: energy systems literacy, project community literacy and political literacy (Cloke, Mohr, & Brown, 2017)
- **Pro-environmental motivation** in participants community energy initiatives leads to higher involvement and identification with the initiative (Sloot, Jans, & Steg, 2018)
- Community-based initiatives in recycling have lower **engagement** than other domains (energy, mobility) (Celata & Sanna, 2019)
- Lack of **transformative** engagement can be caused by: “lack of financial & logistical support, neglect of pre-existing social and political cleavages in society around issues of race, class and gender.” (MacArthur, 2017)
- Local engagement creates a **platform** for climate mitigative action: “At a time when many citizens are losing faith in democratic politics and the state more broadly, local engagement may provide a workaround mechanism to build support for new climate initiatives” (MacArthur, 2017)
- Cultural skew in engaged demographic in Canada, as a major proportion of the energy community demographic consists out of isolated, indigenous communities aiming for innovative funding & local infrastructure (MacArthur, 2017)
- **Crowdfunding** aids engagement through transparency (Dilger, Jovanović, & Voigt, 2017)
- Exploring the ‘materiality of energy democracy’ as part of energy transitions in non-democratic locations (Thailand) where community energy is a practice that does not receive state sanctioning and not with a government apparatus for public engagement – it becomes a site for the making and remaking of public engagement (Delina, 2018)
- Pesch et al (2019) find that engagement may take the shape of: “the strengthening of social capital, the formation of social movements, and the substitution of functions and services.” (Pesch, Spekkink, & Quist, 2019)
- Van Veelen et al (2017) discusses place attachment in Scottish Highlands. They find that, in rural communities, attachment to specific places can either drive development, or lead to disagreement (van Veelen & Haggett, 2017)

- **Procedural justice** (fairness of decision-making process) is identified as an important for local acceptance. In a case study in the UK, fair decision making is mentioned to be important at the start of the process, conflict emerged over the success of this implementation, due to different in normative expectations (Simcock, 2016).

2.4. Social relations & actor roles

The field analysing changes in social relations seems to be broad and at a first glance heterogeneous. There are a number of interesting studies on changing actor configurations and actor roles in the energy transition.

- changes in governance also **across governance levels** from national to local are discussed in a paper by (Saintier, 2017)
- the role of social movements (Hess, 2018)
- “relationship between **local embeddedness** and different forms of organisation and ownership in community energy” (Vancea, Becker, & Kunze, 2017)
- in how far is citizen energy related to **empowerment** (Schreuer, 2016)
- **conflict resolution** in cooperatives finding a strong tendency towards cooperation (Brummer, Herbes, & Gericke, 2017)
- exploring “**irregular connections**” to the urban grid as part of analysis of energy poverty (Angel, 2019)
- Identification of actors in **energy labs** on a community level (Dvarioniene et al., 2015)
- Profiles of **potential investors** into community renewable energy projects (Ebers Broughel & Hampl, 2018)
- the **stakeholder network** around microgeneration in London (Coles, Piterou, & Genus, 2016)
- **Cooperatives** as important players in sustainable energy system and how an orientation toward mutual benefit (rather than public benefit) is associated with lower social identification with the cooperative and weaker ties between members (Bauwens & Defourny, 2017)
- Changing role of the **energy user** within ‘electricity industries’: from clients to citizens, then to consumers and now, in restructured industries, to customers and from there to prosumers, and utility business partners, or potentially even utility competitors, rather than just customers (MacGill & Smith, 2017) – focusing on the challenges such role change poses as well as social benefits
- The priorities (such as ownership, skills and knowledge, service provision, and market commodity) set by actors in the implementation of small-scale technology (e.g. micro hydro plants) can empower people to **acquire different roles**, ranging from engaged consumers (ownership), user-engineer (skills and knowledge), consumer-client (service provision) to prosumers (market commodity) (Hoffken, 2016)
- **mayors** exercise leadership roles in process of establishing a community-owned wind farm include: guarantor, formal convener, facilitator, and sponsor based on authority; tensions arise from citizens’ expectations and personal involvement; there is a positive impact of shared leadership on the effectiveness of the participation process; if they exercise their role(s) adequately, this results in sensitization and mobilization for the issue, weakened opposition, and project adjustment to citizen demands. (Wallmeier & Thaler, 2018)

- opening up the black box of 'community' energy through considering the **role and influence of three actors**: community, state, private sector > inevitably multi-actor processes or 'trans-scalar assemblages of overlapping actors' > need to guard boundaries between actors to also see intermediation and relations (Creamer et al., 2018)
- Privatisation has led to an increase in participation from civil-society in the Philippines, leading to **novel actor constellations** between the distribution utility, local governments and community organisations (Mouton, 2015)
- **Local governments** may play a larger role in community renewable energy, mainly in "facilitating, coordinating and encouraging action through partnerships with private and civil actors." (Mey, Diesendorf, & MacGill, 2016)
- **Local government** plays an important role in realizing locally citizen-led governance in community energy projects in the UK (Van Veelen, 2018)
- A **network of actors** within renewable energy system can facilitate municipal energy system through the establishment of a "local virtual energy cooperative" (Kostevsek et al., 2013)

2.5. Energy justice & inequality

There is a broader literature on energy justice available, in our sample of 172 articles, the following topics linked to energy justice and inequality could be identified:

- (approached as redistribution issue) The making of energy justice in a local community (researched through an initiative of participatory energy budgeting) was linked to issues such as the form of **energy governance** that allows for the participation of citizens and the accountability of the process, policies and technological limitations. (Capaccioli, Poderi, Bettega, & D'Andrea, 2017)
- See also 'narrative' section: Framings of energy justice of activist and advocacy groups are often largely unconnected. They span topics such as energy generation, consumption, distribution and procedure. Authors underline the importance of tracing interconnections between framings to develop a central energy justice frame (Fuller & McCauley, 2016).
- Energy justice was found to be harnessed through social innovation in **business model innovations**, which engaged with knowledge and skill development and building social capital (Hiteva & Sovacool, 2017)
- There is a **lack of policy attention** to provide equal opportunities to different community energy projects, because of an assumption of practical capacities, prioritization for established communities and a technology diffusion emphasis (Park, 2012)
- A **commons approach** to local energy risks increasing inequality, "it also provides opportunities for increasing equality, of wealth, power and individual dignity. These require commitment, and need to be designed into evolving local institutions." (Melville, Burningham, Christie, & Smallwood, 2018)
- **Energy cafes** offer a small step towards decreasing fuel step, through local economic development and increasing health equality (Martiskainen, Heiskanen, & Speciale, 2018)
- Firestone et al (2018) reviews that for processes to be fair, wind power developers have to be open in **communication** (Firestone et al., 2018).

2.6. Gender

A gendered perspective on the energy transition is not part of mainstream research. Nevertheless, some researchers have looked into gender issues. However, as research into SI is an emerging field and gender research in energy is also a niche, few papers combine both aspects so far.

- Some papers deal with **energy poverty** in relation to gender (Listo, 2018; Pachauri & Rao, 2013)
- (Standal, Talevi, & Westskog, 2020) analyse **prosuming** applying a gender lense: “the article pays particular attention to how the phases of appropriation, objectification, incorporation and conversion of household solar systems are gendered in the sense that women and men have different economic, social and cultural capital”
- “ultimately discuss gender equality and justice, and the lack thereof, in energy decision making” in a study on stakeholder insights into the low-carbon energy transition in Spain (Sorman, García-Muros, Pizarro-Irizar, & González-Eguino, 2020)
- looking into everyday consumption and practices (Greene, 2018)
- in relation to activism grass-root-activities (Willow & Keefer, 2015)
- home comfort (Hansen et al. 2019)

Background literature

- (Kaijser & Kronsell, 2014) apply the concept of **intersectionality** from critical feminist theory to climate change - a paper that could contribute to developing a framework
- (Søraa et al., 2020) look across H2020 projects and comes to the conclusion: “Our study shows that, in spite of such ambitions, there was huge variety with regard to how gender was understood as well as how notions of gender were engaged with during the project. Dealing with gender was often reduced to counting men and women, while wider concerns, such as representations of age, geography, field of expertise, etc., were comparatively neglected. In this paper, we argue that **gender equality strategies** should embrace these wider perspectives to sufficiently address how various forms of intersectionality may inform and strengthen inclusive engagement.”
- The underlying SHAPE-project also published a report (Søraa et al., 2020) (Anfinsen und Heidenreich 2017)
- (Terry, 2009) look into climate justice and gender (with a focus on developing countries)

Broader subjects that could be relevant for SIE: **professional participation** of men and women

- “By looking at engineering in the area of renewable energies, this paper analyses how **hierarchical gender relations** are discursively (re)produced or challenged at the symbolic level within the context of the so-called energy transition.” (Priestl, 2019)
- Participation of women in an educational programme of **MEnS ("Meeting Energy Professional Skills")**, an H2020 project focused on providing high quality upskilling and education to architects, engineers, and building professionals (Peñalvo-López & Cárcel-Carrasco, 2019)
- **Gender diverse workforce** in the renewable energy transition (Pearl-Martinez & Stephens, 2016)

2.7. Motivation

- **Remarkable difference in the interests** of the main actors in community wind power projects in Japan, including economic interests and a sense of social commitment, participation and contribution (Maruyama, Nishikido, & Iida, 2007)
- **Pro-environmental motivation** leads to higher participation (Sloot et al., 2018), see also ‘participation’ section
- **Younger and smaller cooperatives** are more likely to widen their market, than older cooperatives that focus on the local environment (Stoll, Poon, & Hamilton, 2015)
- Grassroots innovators are primarily motivated to increase **value for others**, rather than value for themselves (Ross, Mitchell, & May, 2012)
- Following the Chernobyl disaster and a regime in West-Germany harnessing a fearful discourse, citizen-led initiatives were motivated to socially construct a sense of **human security** and emerged to mitigate a similar disaster (Arndt, 2010).
- **Energy consumption levels** in 10 Australian houses (monitored over the course of a year) was linked to the type of technology used, and individual behaviours and motivations. “individuals living in the same house may have different motivations and/or heating and cooling practices, affecting the overall energy use” (Eon, Morrison, & Byrne, 2018)
- Different motivations of **retail investments** in renewable energy projects, defined as “local patriots” and “yield investors”, where the former group use simple decision metrics and gut feeling to make decisions (Salm, Hille, & Wustenhagen, 2016)

2.8. Narratives/imaginaries/frames/discourses

Much of this literature analyses competing framings and their performativity.

- Narratives about **new energy landscapes**, i.e. sustainable energy systems need to be about “endeavour, solidarity, enterprise, community and purpose” (Llewellyn, Rohse, Day, & Fyfe, 2017)
- **national imaginaries** (of bioenergy) are interpreted differently by local and nonlocal actors involved in community sitings of proposed facilities; framing processes are related to social movements which unite around competing collective memories of place (collective action frames) (Eaton, Gasteyer, & Busch, 2014)
- Greater likelihood of success for energy transitions with **public engagement and public acceptance**, but most research focuses on technological innovation for energy production and consumption. Takes the sociotechnical imaginary of a more participatory idea of smart cities emerging from practices (i.e. community energy research) vs. the more technocratic emerging from research on smart energy systems. (Corsini, Certoma, Dyer, & Frey, 2019)
- **Framings of the coalmining opposition** in the Czech Republic include three frames: Local Impact frame, the Low-Carbon Transition frame, and the Anti-Systemic Environmental frame; the opposition is thus not homogenous and the drivers are based in ideological orientations withering the ‘nimby’ frame (Cernoch, Lehotsky, Ocelik, Osicka, & Vencourova, 2019)
- **Politics of mobility**: where dominant/institutional discourses privilege individualised automobility related to morality, modernity and freedom; while everyday discourses both reinforce and challenge

those and show the interwovenness: argues that the “idea that the behaviour change of a solitary mobile subject holds the key to solve the problems caused by increasing car use has to be abandoned for the understanding that mobile lives are socially, culturally and materially relational” (Doughty & Murray, 2016)

- **Framings of energy justice** of activist and advocacy groups are often largely unconnected. They span topics such as energy generation, consumption, distribution and procedure. Authors underline the importance of tracing interconnections between framings to develop a central energy justice frame (Fuller & McCauley, 2016).
- Populism: **framings of anti-smart meter activism** are analyzed to be populist framings, as these movements are not necessarily engaged with the technology itself, but rather oppose the technology beyond the consumer impact (Kallman & Frickel, 2019)
- Community-based initiatives should “draw on multiple discourses to address individual interests (such as stable prices and supply security) and collective concerns (environmental protection).” This is because of the diversity of the “dispersed agency” of institutional entrepreneurs at diverse phases of development (Mahzouni, 2019)

2.9. Other

- Institutional factors and local norms are essential for the emergence of cooperatives (S. Wirth, 2014). Examples are familiarity with local ownership in Danish culture, stimulating the emergence of wind cooperatives (Gorroño-Albizu, Sperling, & Djørup, 2019), and cultural tradition in establishing cooperatives in south Tyrol, Italy (S. Wirth, 2014).
- incentives and advisory services from the federal government are key to developing the capacity of American Indian tribes to pursue energy planning and energy resource development; these promote tribal control over energy planning and energy resource development efforts (Brookshire & Kaza, 2013)

3. Some observations about and gaps in the current literature

- This is a vast array of heterogeneous papers that have been tagged as being related to ‘socio-cultural’ aspects of social innovation in energy.
- Literature on the significance of places/spatial dimensions is mentioned in relation to social acceptance but also linked to social relations.
- The literature on social acceptance and the literature on participation shows considerable overlap, since participation is considered to increase social acceptance.
- About social acceptance, few studies looked into this concept while simultaneously considering the new developments under study as a social innovation. Moreover, most research into social acceptance focuses on the public as an actor (Wolsink, 2019)

- There is interesting work that broadens the understanding of participation beyond the state-centered understanding of the participation of citizens or even the participation in organised events and processes, but includes everyday practice as participation in energy
- There are a number of frameworks used, a preliminary list;
 - o Energy culture framework (Ambrosio-Albala et al., 2019)
 - o Energy landscape (Llewellyn et al., 2017)
 - o Ecologies of participation (Chilvers et al., 2018)
 - o Frame analysis; related to social movement (Cernoch et al., 2019; Eaton et al., 2014)
 - o Imaginaries (Corsini et al., 2019; Eaton et al., 2014)
 - o ...

4. What questions arise for SONNET?

- Which of the different analytical lenses/concepts to use as an entry point? Studies seem to take a specific perspective as entry point, e.g. social acceptance and then link this to trust, participation, procedural justice etc. This means that for SONNET it is important to make a choice in this array of possible entry points for the analysis of socio-cultural aspects and entangle the 'knot' from there.
- How can we build on this literature in developing a framework to analyse changes in social relations and roles?
- Consider autarchy as a dimension of SIE with a psychological and a technical dimension; consider implications for the system level for which self-reliance and autarchy are not likely to be efficient approaches
- identify and study the specific implications for social acceptance in relation to SIE
- systematically use a 'gendered perspective' on social innovation:
 - o do men, women, diverse individuals participate differently in SIE, i.e. do they join and support SIEs to different level or extent, do they engage in different types of activities, do they have varying preferences?
 - o in how far do SIE contribute to replicate traditional role models or to break them up?
- ...

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Research Brief #7: *A socio-political focus on social innovation in energy: drivers, barriers and contributions.*

SONNET RESEARCH BRIEF

A socio-political focus on social innovation in energy: drivers, barriers and contributions

Maria Stadler, Flor Avelino, Heike Brugger, Marta Strumińska-Kutra and Karoline Rogge

Aim of the brief: to define the socio-political issues/ themes relevant for SONNET and identify existing themes and gaps in the current literature grounded on SONNET Mendeley literature database

Preamble: Reflections on conducting the review

- This research brief starts with a general review of the socio-political SIE literature included in the SONNET Mendeley database (MS, with feedback from KR); the research gaps identified in this literature are derived at the end of this first section.
- The brief then continues with four deep-dive sections split up according to focus in WP2 tasks: governance arrangements (MSK, T2.1), policy networks (HB, T2.2), power (FA, T2.3), and policy mixes (KR, T2.4)
- This research brief should be read as work in progress, or as starting point for the engagement with the academic literature of relevance for WP 2 and the socio-political cross-cutting theme.

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OVERVIEW OF THE SOCIO-POLITICAL LITERATURE IN MENDELEY SIE-DATABASE (MARIA STADLER)

Introduction

This first section aims for providing a broad overview of the socio-political literature used in SONNET (130 papers in total) and will describe its main keywords, research topics, methods and theories as well as investigated actors and scales. The Sections two to five of this brief will deepen the main socio-political research themes of the SONNET project (these research themes are: Collaborative governance arrangements for SIE, Policy Networks for SIE, Power dynamics between SIE and dominant institutions and policy mixes for SIE).

Themes and research topics

Keywords: The keywords used in the examined literature (130 papers) address (among others) the following themes and research topics: social movements (13), governance (11), social innovation (10), energy democracy (9), processes (7), energy policy (7), success (6), participation and participatory governance (6), conditions (5), acceptance (3).

What do we know from the literature? The socio-political literature on SIE puts a focus on (shifting) power relations (e.g. Avelino und Wittmayer 2016; Brisbois 2019) and participatory governance arrangements (e.g. Shin und Lee 2017; Komendantova et al. 2018; Krupa et al. 2015). The changes in power relations are e.g. described using the term 'energy democracy' (e.g. Becker und Naumann 2017; Burke und Stephens 2017; Delina 2018a, 2018b; Szulecki 2018). Research in this thematic field e.g. tries to link the perspectives of top-down arrangements and bottom-up movements (e.g. Akizu et al. 2018; Bickerstaff et al. 2016). Further, research questions address the subjects of energy justice (e.g. Hiteva und Sovacool 2017), energy poverty (e.g. Hackett 2016) or acceptance (e.g. Hunt 2017). Many approaches investigate (power) relations within the energy transition from an interpretative perspective on discourses (e.g. Doughty und Murray 2016) and framings (e.g. Daub 2010) or examine future imaginaries (e.g. Ruotsalainen et al. 2016). On the other hand, research questions ask about concrete barriers and conflicts (e.g. Neukirch 2016; Mey et al. 2016; Proka et al. 2018) or, in contrast, about (financial) incentives for a successful energy transition (e.g. Curtin et al. 2017; Gui et al. 2017; Grashof 2019).

Initial reflections on research gaps: *linking interpretive approaches with the analysis of concrete regulations, barriers and incentives; analysing policy mixes as complex combination of long term visions and concrete instruments; examining the dynamics within top-down arrangements (not as fixed structures,*

which are challenged by niches, but as fluctuating themselves); interesting to examine examples of failure and conflict;

What questions arise for SONNET? *analysing the dynamics within policy networks as well as the dynamics within community energy projects; combining top-down and bottom-up perspectives; analysing policy mixes;*

Focus on empirical rather than conceptual studies

Keywords: The empirical focus is on case study designs, fewer studies concentrate on rather conceptual developments (only 13 papers use the keyword 'conceptual'). The empirical data on which the studies are based, come from cases in Europe (47) - with a larger number of studies in the UK (23) and Germany (16) - as well as from outside Europe (32). The socio-political themes often raise crosscutting issues with socio-cultural (38) and socio-economic (22) questions.

Theoretically, studies on socio-political aspects of SIE draw on approaches such as multi-level perspective (e.g. Capellán-Pérez et al. 2018), strategic niche management (e.g. Smith et al. 2016), strategic action fields (e.g. Fuchs und Hinderer 2016), institutional theories (e.g. Hoicka und MacArthur 2018), neoliberalism (e.g. Hess 2011), neo-Polanyian theory (e.g. Pearse 2016) and actor-network-theory (e.g. van der Schoor et al. 2016).

Empirically, there is a strong focus on qualitative (comparative) case studies (e.g. Ferguson-Martin und Hill 2011) which are in some cases also combined with survey data and document analyses (e.g. Howard 2015; Berka et al. 2017). Other studies take a historical perspectives and describe the development of transitions (e.g. Bargheer 2018; Mey und Diesendorf 2018). Fewer studies are based on mappings (e.g. Chilvers et al. 2018), one on text mining (Sung und Park 2018).

Initial reflections on research gaps: *Zolfagharian et al. (2019) criticises that there is a too strong focus in qualitative case studies; suggests more studies on cross-country comparisons but also mix-method approaches as helpful; different interdisciplinary approaches but lack of conceptual framework to distinguish SIE*

Questions for SONNET: *conceptual framework: how to describe the complexities of changing as well as 'dominant' structures?*

Actors or who is studied?

Keywords: There is a strong focus on community (renewable) energy projects (43), community engagement (32), civil society (10), the role of citizen (6) cooperative(s) (9) and grassroots (5). In some studies consumers (2) or - more often - prosumer(s) (8) are studied. Fewer papers investigate intermediaries and inter-organizational networks (3) or actors in the field of politics (4).

What do we know from the literature? A larger group of studies concentrates on the actors involved in community energy groups and cooperatives. Seyfang et al. (2013) investigate 'the objectives, origins and development' (978) of community energy projects in the UK while Martiskainen et al. (2018) ask 'how community energy initiatives perform particular forms of everyday politics' (21). Furthermore, Bomberg and McEwen (2012) concentrate on the question how groups mobilize to overcome barriers and conclude that 'success fulmobilization depends on how well groups exploit state resources and mitigate those constraints' (442). The studies of Höfer et al. (2015) and Brummer (2018), on the other hand, examine the dynamics within these groups. Höfer et al. use an experimental approach to investigate cooperative governance structures and investment behaviour while Brummer concentrates on internal decision-making processes. Since SIE can be understood as multi actor phenomenon, Avelino und Wittmayer (2016) use a multi-actor perspective to analyse shifting power relations and the changing role of civil society. By doing so, they not only differentiate between different forms of power but also ask about who is meant by the broader category of 'civil society' actors. Another focus is put on the question of how private consumers transform into prosumers (Inderberg et al. 2018, e.g.; Kotilainen und Saari 2018) and the legal context of peer-to-peer trading (e.g. van Soest 2019). In the literature under review, few studies primarily focus on policy makers. However, Hindmarsh und Alidoust (2019) ask 'how policymakers can better engage with the concerns of citizens' and Horváthová und Dobbins (2019) draw on the question 'how open existing structures are for citizen's inputs'. Some studies also investigate intermediaries, (e.g. Mignon und Kanda 2018) ask about similarities and differences among intermediaries and their role in sustainability transitions. Collaborations and networks between actors from different fields are analysed e.g. by Canzler et al. (2017) who ask about new forms of collaborations in living labs or by Maruyama et al. (2007) who study the complexity of networks and the heterogeneity of actors' interests from actor-network-theory perspective.

Initial reflections on research gaps: *Interactions between different actors on different levels still understudied; actors different and sometimes conflicting parallel roles as policy makers and consumers; changes in actors' roles over time; intermediaries and their roles;*

What questions arise for SONNET? *forms of collaboration between community energy groups and policy makers/city administration; how do SIE relate to different scales? how to shape conditions on different scales? social innovation in within political field?*

Scale and spatiality

Keywords: The literature under review addresses questions on different scales: The focus here is on questions related to locality, localism and local initiatives (18). Also, the spatial dimension of decentralization of the energy system (10) as well as urban contexts of SIE are studied (8). Fewer studies investigate SIE under consideration of their European or international embeddedness.

What do we know from the literature? The literature under review differs according to the scale (local, regional, national and international level) on which studies are based. The focus is on local initiatives and context conditions. Devine-Wright and Wiersma (2013) e.g., aim to open up 'the local to analysis', Eagle et al. (2017) analyse strategies of localism and Hasanov and Zuidema (2018) develop a 'conceptual framework for understanding local energy initiatives'. Also urban contexts and the role of cities are of regarded, e.g. in the studies of Becker et al. (2016) who explore 'new geographies of coproduction

emerging in urban energy politics' or in the paper of Blanchet (2015) who discuss 'the scope and limits' of local initiatives in an urban context. (Nerini et al. (2019) argue that 'cities will play a key role in achieving' climate action goals and provide an 'overview of key areas that will need research and innovation to support the decarbonisation challenge in the European Union' (2). Few papers also raise question concerning the possibilities of scaling up local initiatives. E.g. Lutz et al. (2017) ask for transition strategies on regional level to inspire governance on national level while Pellicer-Sifres et al. (2018) and Sareen et al. (2018) emphasize the need to scale up the learnings from local innovations and test fields. In some studies, the interplay between different scales are addressed, e.g. Lemon et al. (2015) ask how national energy policy translates to the local level and Peters et al. (2012) analyse the link between bottom-up groups and decision makers, starting from the local level. De Leeuw und Groenleer (2018) point on the regional level and ask what factors shape regional energy governance. European policy conditions are rarely addressed, however Tosun et al. (2019) compare the motivation for engagement in national vs. European politics and find that engagement in energy governance is primarily affected by path-dependence.

Initial reflections on research gaps: *gap in linking the different scales between local, regional, national and international level. Analysing interlinkages could contribute to better understanding the conditions for scaling up local initiatives. gap in analysing the interplay of policy (making? instruments? processes?) on different scales;*

What questions arise for SONNET? *role of EU policy structures for SIE? conditions for scaling up? conditions for SIE on larger scales?*

Research gaps

Based on the 130 academic articles in the SONNET Mendeley database which have been tagged as socio-political we identified all future research needs indicated by the authors of these studies (for a detailed overview, see the following document in the SONNET cloud:

<https://owncloud.fraunhofer.de/index.php/f/78760832>). Based on this, we have summarized the identified research gaps into the following themes. A closer examination, reflection and interpretation of these gaps is still outstanding, and will partly be already taken up in the following sections with their governance, network, power and policy mix focus.

- **Cases:** need to study different empirical cases for cross-country comparison
- **Actors:** who are the actors involved? Possible conflicts between actors are so far understudied as well as the boundaries between actors (e.g. different motivations of different actors; differences in motivation and behaviour; complexity and differences within local groups; interactions between local actors and dominant institutions; intermediaries as group of actors and their differences; strategies of incumbents). Need to specify certain groups of actors (e.g. who is 'the city?')
- **Locality:** the local as 'scale of interest'. Questions, which arise here are e.g.: What is considered local? How to generalize from the local to a larger scale? How to take heterogeneity into account?

- **Spatiality:** lack of studies on the spatiality of the energy transition
- **Scales and practices:** need to take multiple scales into account; addressing the connection of instruments to every-day life and every-day practices; studying the linkages between government level and every-day life; studying the impact of external factors(beyond the national context); asking about the possibilities and limits of 'scaling things up'
- **Technology-centred questions:** how to shape policy instruments and legal frameworks for new technological possibilities? lack of social studies compared to technical studies (disciplines involved in research?)
- **Structural perspective:** asking about the degree of professionalization of local level initiatives; What role do networks play in institutionalizing small scale groups?
- **Participatory governance:** Studying different levels and forms of participation;
- **Power:** Studying power shifts and their consequences; studying informal deliberative mechanisms
- **Energy democracy:** lack of studies which address energy democracy in non-democratic countries, the developing world, the role of minority groups
- **Methodological:** lack of macro-studies
- **Theoretical:** lack of theoretical frameworks
- **Context:** need to analyse barriers for community projects as well as enabling conditions
- **Governance:** asking about governance frameworks of community groups, distributional justice; community as a means of governing
- **Financial conditions:** analysing the costs and risks of community energy; conditions of financial participation, shared ownership; lack of focus on business model innovations; in contrast: also addressing sustainable degrowth; need to critical examine funding conditions of community groups; investor led governance
- **Labs:** studying living labs

Some final notes: process of institutionalization; degree of institutionalization; intermediaries and networks as links between niches and dominant regime (studying the-in-between concerning scale, actors, institutionalization)

Core papers

Avelino, F. and Wittmayer, J. (2016): Shifting Power Relations in Sustainability Transitions. A Multi-actor Perspective. In *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning* 18 (5), pp. 628–649. DOI: 10.1080/1523908X.2015.1112259.

Devine-Wright, P.; Wiersma, B. (2013): Opening up the "local" to analysis. Exploring the spatiality of UK urban decentralised energy initiatives. In *LOCAL ENVIRONMENT* 18 (10), pp. 1099–1116. DOI: 10.1080/13549839.2012.754742.

Mignon, I.; Kanda, W. (2018): A typology of intermediary organizations and their impact on sustainability transition policies. In *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions* 29, pp. 100–113. DOI: 10.1016/j.eist.2018.07.001.

van der Schoor, Tineke; van Lente, Harro; Scholtens, Bert; Peine, Alexander (2016): Challenging obduracy. How local communities transform the energy system. In *ENERGY RESEARCH & SOCIAL SCIENCE* 13, pp. 94–105. DOI: 10.1016/j.erss.2015.12.009.

2 GOVERNANCE (MARTA STRUMIŃSKA-KUTRA)

What do we know from the literature? ¹

Governance is understood here as an approach to public management and policy making that

- a) adopts hybrid practices, combining administrative systems with market mechanisms and non-profit organizations,
- b) is multijurisdictional by combining people and institutions across different policy sectors and different levels of government and
- c) encompasses multiple stakeholders linked together in networks (Bevir, 2011, pp. 2-3).

This definition is broad enough to capture concepts like New Public Governance (Sørensen & Torfing, 2015), collaborative governance (Ansell & Gash, 2008), participatory governance (Shin & Lee, 2017), public governance (Kordasiewicz & Sadura, 2017; Sørensen & Torfing, 2015) and to capture interactive nature of governance (Sørensen & Torfing, 2018).

Despite of some critical discussions highlighting the tension between effectiveness and democratization, there is a relatively broad consensus that collaboration between relevant and affected social and political actors introduced by governance arrangements tends to improve the definition of problems, generate a greater richness of ideas, stimulate mutual learning, build joint ownership, facilitate coordinated implementation, and diffuse innovative solutions to new contexts (Hartley, Sørensen, & Torfing, 2013).

From the perspective of SONNET the most interesting approaches to governance are those directly referring to governance as an arrangement facilitating (collaborative) innovation (Chris Ansell & Gash, 2012; Bommert, 2010; Borins, 2014; Torfing & Triantafillou, 2016) and evolutionary learning for public goals, where diverse stakeholders “learn how to refine and improve their values, knowledge, and practice in a continuous fashion” (Ansell, 2011, p. 9).

Interestingly enough the literature review on city labs revealed that the method itself is explicitly understood as a new governance model aiming at collaborative problem solving and facilitation of learning (Scholl et al., 2018). For example (Giannouli et al., 2018) presents regional living labs as a tool for governing of changes in energy systems that involve a multi-level and multiple-stakeholder group process of shared governance. The goal of their research was to create an environment for experimental learning and an institutional framework that might support the process of decision-making and institutional development – in this sense city labs can actually be understood as a meta-governance tool: tool for correcting failures that each type of governance (through networks, markets, hierarchies, (Jessop, 2011) tend to make. A good example of this approach is a city lab in Leeds, that was explicitly designed to respond to deficits in contemporary urban governance, especially relating to

¹ Going back to Mendeley literature still necessary - although an important note - there only are 13 articles with a key word governance (one with participatory governance).

participation and disenfranchisement, and ultimately unlock improved ways of designing, managing and living in cities (Chatterton, Owen, Cutter, Dymski, & Unsworth, 2018).

Significantly – the literature, especially (Giannouli et al., 2018; Scholl et al., 2018) indicate that practicing governance as well as implementation of procedures and solutions ‘produced’ in labs demands building of institutional infrastructure – changes in existing rules and procedures and or introduction of new ones, building new communication channels, creation of new organizational roles. Chatterton et al. indicate that both implementing city labs and introducing changes in governance patterns requires moving beyond traditional organizational identities and working practices (see also Strumińska-Kutra, 2018).

What are the research gaps?

- What are the boundary conditions for evolutionary learning?
- What is the role of collective for learning and innovating?
- How does learning become institutionalized in (public) organizations?

What questions arise for SONNET?

Main research question:

- How to build institutional and organizational infrastructure enabling collaboration and evolutionary learning?

Research sub-questions:

- What is the role of diverse institutional and organizational context for the process of introducing dialogue based, collaborative approaches to governance?
- How to build institutional and organizational reflexivity (ability to critically reflect on action and its assumptions as well as ability to correct them)?

What are key readings?

Chatterton et al. (2018): institutional innovation, emotions, change of procedures and identities

Giannouli et al. (2018): institutional and individual capacity building (for governance – yet mainly cognitive and normative perspective, without pointing out organizational solutions)

Scholl et al. (2018): ‘embedding novel governance models in organizations’, embedding of lessons learnt

3 POLICY NETWORKS (HEIKE BRUGGER)

What do we know from the literature?

We know from the literature that actor constellations play a crucial role for SIE and for local transitions. In case studies often the importance of (a group of) single actors who pushed the transition (or certain aspects of it) is emphasized (Große et al., 2016; Radtke, 2016). Whether these actors are able to accelerate the transition in their region seems to highly depend on their ability to mobilize others within the region (Bouwhuis, 2016; Blanchet, 2014; Feldhoff, 2016; Hess 2019) - for which preexisting social (trust) networks might be crucial (Catney et. al. 2013; deLeeuw & Groenleer, 2018). As well as to network with higher-level actors that support their aims and other cities that follow a similar path (Kern and Bulkeley, 2009).

Policy network analysis allows for a structured and comparative analysis of beneficial and conflicting relations in which the SIE-initiatives are embedded in, including the relations to various policy relevant actors (Bomberg & McEwen 2012). This approach identifies structures in actor relations, such as the importance of actors, the density of relations, and the presence of supporting or conflicting relationships (Wasserman & Faust, 1994; Scott, 2000; Henry & Vollan, 2014). It is therefore the prime choice for analysing how certain actor constellations can enhance or inhibit the development of SIE-initiatives.

The importance of networks has been emphasized and studied in many research fields, which are of direct relevance to the SONNET project, including the diffusion of (social) innovation (Murray et al., 2010), sustainable development (Henry & Vollan, 2014).

What are the research gaps?

- Many single case studies in which actor constellations are qualitatively described and in which their importance is pointed out exist (Feldhoff, 2016; Bouwhuis, 2016; Wirth et al., 2013; Faller, 2016). However, comparative case studies are much less present, while they are the only possible way to understand broader pattern. A comparative and quantitative network analysis is a prime method to close this gap and make the question of actor constellations measurable and thus comparable (Brugger, 2017).
- A holistic approach of studying actor constellations is missing (Henry & Vollan 2014): Based on the questions of **what favourable network structures are** and **how they are formed**, the third questions **How can favourable policy networks be created?** can be answered for the SIEs, delivering practice-oriented information and guidance for cities and initiatives of how to "take their luck into their own hands" based on forming conditions that support the evolution of favourable network structures.

- Both research gaps (single vs. comparative cases and partial vs. holistic approach) are not only existing for SIEs at the local level, but in the general work on actor constellations. Therefore, SONNET can fill an important void by tackling both gaps in the comparative, qualitative and quantitative analysis planned.

What questions arise for SONNET?

Following Henry and Vollan (2014) the research questions arising for SONNET are structured under three main questions, which are crucial for the understanding of policy networks:

1. How do network structures influence the outcomes of SIE-initiatives at the local level?
 - Which structures are observed in the policy networks surrounding SIE-initiatives (e.g. importance of actors, density of relations, and presence of supporting or conflicting relationships)? (Descriptive network analysis)
 - How can certain actor constellations enhance or inhibit the development of SIE-initiatives? (Comparative, quantitative network analysis)
 - Are patterns identifiable between certain structures and certain outcomes (e.g. are initiatives more successful in diffusing their outreach, when supporting relationships of municipal actors are intense?)
2. How do networks around SIE-initiatives at the local level self-organize?
 - Understanding the rationale behind the creation of relations in the context of SIEs on the local level: Why do people interact with the people they do? Why do they not interact with other actors with whom relations are theoretical possible? (Quantitative network analysis and qualitative analysis of interview questions)
3. How do institutions shape networks surrounding SIE-initiatives?
 - How can beneficial network structures be created (e.g. do successful formats exist in some cities, which allow to close structural gaps by bringing relevant people together?) (Qualitative analysis of interview questions)

What are key readings?

Henry, A.D., Vollan, B., 2014. Networks and the Challenge of Sustainable Development. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources* 39, 583–610.

Kern, K., Bulkeley, H., 2009. Cities, Europeanization and Multi-level Governance: Governing Climate Change through Transnational Municipal Networks*. *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies* 47, 309–332. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-5965.2009.00806.x>

4 POWER (FLOR AVELINO)

A few reflections on doing the literature review

To gain insight on power insights relevant for SONNET, I would argue for a power-specific review of the following fields/ topics:

- power – energy studies
- power – sustainability transitions (general)
- power – sustainability transitions in energy
- power – social innovation (general)
- power – social innovation in energy

I have not done a systematic literature review (yet) of these fields and topics, nor of the SONNET literature base (which includes some of the above topics). I hope to conduct some of this literature review in the coming months.

My answers to the questions below are based on my general knowledge of the fields of sustainability transitions, social innovation and power studies. As such they are hypothetical answers to need to be verified.

What do we know from the literature?

Power is one of the most contested concepts in social and political theory. There have been several critical interrogations on the role of power and politics in both fields of social innovation and sustainability transitions (e.g. Swyngedow_2005; Shove & Walker_2007; Moulaert_etal._2007; Hendriks_2009; Meadowcroft 2009; Voß_etal._2009; Smith & Stirling_2010; Kern_2011; Hess_2013; Scoones_et al._2015; Brandsen_etal._2016; Ayob et al. 2016). These are often accompanied/ followed by attempts to review literature on power and to synthesize conceptualizations of power in relation to innovation and transformative change (e.g. Grin_2010, Hoffman_2013, Geels_2014, Partzsch 2017, Ahlborg_2017, Avelino 2017, Brisbois 2019, Sovacool & Brisbois 2019). Several of these studies have focused on the energy sector.

Interestingly, both the concepts of ‘transitions’ and ‘social innovation’ have been defined – either implicitly or explicitly – in terms of shifting (power) relations. This makes the understanding of power relations – and how they change – a necessary condition for understanding processes of (transformative) social innovation.

In the broadest sense of the word, we can understand power dialectically as the *relational and structural (in)capacity of actors to mobilise resources and institutions to achieve a goal* (Avelino 2017). As one of the most contested concepts in social and political theory, power definitions range from actor- specific resources used in the pursuit of self-interests (Weber_1946) to the capacity of social systems to mobilize resources for collective goals (Parsons_1967). Following interpretations of power as an ‘essentially contested’ ‘family resemblance concept’ (Lukes_1974; Haugaard_2002), we can identify seven prevailing points of contestations: (1) power ‘over’ vs. power ‘to’, (2) centred vs. diffused, (3) consensual vs.

conflictual, (4) constraining vs. enabling, (5) empowerment vs. disempowerment, (6) power = knowledge vs. power \neq knowledge, and (7) power as means versus power as an end in itself (Avelino 2011, 2018, see also table 1 below). For each of these contestations, we can explore how different scholars (e.g. Arendt_1969, Clegg_1989, Parsons_1967, Lukes_1974, Foucault_1980, Giddens_1984, Flyvbjerg_1998, Haugaard_2002) dealt with these contestations and what they imply for investigating power in the context of processes of social innovation and transitions. Rather than 'choosing sides' within these debates or attempting to 'solve' them, we can acknowledge the different dimensions of these power contestations (see table 1).

What are the research gaps?

While there is increasing attention to notions and theories of power in the fields of transition research and energy studies, and – to a lesser extent – in social innovation research, there has – as far as I know – not yet been research that explicitly links social innovation in energy transitions in explicit power terms. I would argue this is particularly problematic because much research about innovation and transformative change in the energy sector tends to *implicitly revolve around issues of power*.

With its thematic focus and inclusion of social scientists who specialize in issues of power and politics in innovation and change, SONNET has the potential to fill that research gap to a certain extent, both conceptually and empirically.

What questions arise for SONNET?

Power question for SONNET:

- How are power relations changing (or not) in/ through SIE: who is holding, gaining, losing, exercising or undergoing power in/ through SIE processes?
- How are existing power structures transformed and/ or reproduced through SIE?
- What are the countervailing powers of SIE initiatives and networks to challenge, alter and replace incumbent / regime initiatives and networks in energy? What evidence can we find of such countervailing powers?
- What are the power dynamics in sustainable energy transitions? How do the power dynamics of SIE relate to the power dynamics in sustainable energy transitions?

Each of these questions can be specified in various ways, depending on which theories of power we utilize. Table 1 on the next page provides an overview of what kind of empirical power questions could be asked about SIE.

Table 1: Diverse power questions about social innovation in energy (adopted from Avelino 2018)

<p>Power Theory Contestations</p>	<p>Questions about social innovation in energy (SIE) (to be elaborated, selected and operationalised)</p>
<p>Power ‘over’ <> power ‘to’ (e.g. Dahl, Parsons, Foucault, Morris, Davis, Giddens, Arendt, Gordon, Stewart)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Power to</i>: How is what kind of power exercised for/through/against SIE? How are which resources mobilised? • <i>Power over</i>: Who is exercising power over whom? How are which structures of domination/ oppression/ dependence changed or (re)produced? • <i>Power with</i>: What are the power coalitions that enable/resist SEI, and how do actors collaborate in the exercise of power?
<p>Centred <> diffused (e.g. Dahl, Bachrach & Baratz, Lukes, Mann, Foucault, Gramsci)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How are the three/four faces of power manifested in SIE? • Who are the TSI elites, who sets the agenda, which issues are on/off the agenda, how are preferences shaped? Who is included and excluded? • How is power diffused, (de)centralised and/or recentralised by SIE?
<p>Consensual <> conflictual (e.g. Parsons, Arendt, Mann, Haugaard)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How are both consensus and conflict manifested in SIE? • Which conflicts are ‘hidden’ under seemingly consensual processes? • (How) is consensus oppressive, how is conflict emancipatory, and vice versa?
<p>Constraining <> enabling (e.g. Foucault, Giddens, Clegg, Davis, Arendt, Hayward & Lukes)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How are both structure & agency manifested in SIE? Who is enabled and who is constrained in SIE, how and by whom or what? • How/to what extent are which structures (a) an object of SIE (to be transformed), (b) a constraint for SIE, (c) an enabler for SIE?
<p>Empowerment <> disempowerment (e.g. Boje & Rosile, Hardy & Leiba-O’Sullivan, Follet)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who is (dis)empowered in/by SIE, by whom or by what? • (How) is (dis)empowerment manifested in TSI as (a) intentional outcome (empowerment as end), (b) constraining/enabling factor (empowerment as means), or (c) object/type of SIE in itself?
<p>Knowledge as <> prior to power (e.g. Bourdieu, Flyvbjerg, Lukes, Foucault, Barnes)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How is knowledge in/for SIE organised, for and by whom? • How is knowledge manifested as (a) an object of change & SIE, or (b) an instrument for enabling/constraining SIE? • What are the discourses and ideologies underlying SIE?
<p>Power as means vs. power as an end in itself (e.g. Foucault, Arendt, Haugaard)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which power relations are implied by future visions of SIE? • What are (un)intended consequences of SIE in power terms? • What are the power-ethical issues in SIE from both an empirical and normative political theory point of view?

What are key readings?

- Ahlborg, H. (2017). Towards a conceptualization of power in energy transitions. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 25, 122-141.
- Avelino, F. (2018), Power Contestations: what different theories of power mean for social innovation research, Paper presented at the *International Social Innovation Research Conference*, Heidelberg, 3-5th of September 2018.
- Avelino, F. (2017) Power in Sustainability Transitions. Analysing Power and (Dis)Empowerment in Transformative Change towards Environmental and Social Sustainability, *Journal of Environmental Policy & Governance*, 27(6): 505–520 <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/eet.1777/full>
- Ayob, N., Teasdale, S., & Fagan, K. (2016). How Social Innovation ‘Came to Be’: Tracing the Evolution of a Contested Concept. *Journal of Social Policy*, 45(4), 635-653. doi:10.1017/S004727941600009X
- Brisbois, M. C. (2019). Powershifts: A framework for assessing the growing impact of decentralized ownership of energy transitions on political decision-making. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 50, 151-161.
- Hayward, C., & Lukes, S. (2008). Nobody to shoot? Power, structure, and agency: A dialogue. *Journal of Power*, 1(1): 5-20.
- Sovacool, B. K., & Brisbois, M. C. (2019). Elite power in low-carbon transitions: A critical and interdisciplinary review, *Energy Research & Social Science*, 57, 101242.
- Stirling, A. (2014). Transforming power: Social science and the politics of energy choices. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 1, 83-95.

5 POLICY MIXES (KAROLINE ROGGE)

What do we know from the literature?

Over the past decade increasing attention has been given to the role that policy mixes – also referred to as policy packages or policy portfolios - play for sustainable low-carbon transitions in various sectors, such as in energy (Rogge et al., 2017), transport (Givoni et al., 2013), industry (Scordato et al., 2018), agri-food (Kalfagianni and Kuik, 2017) or forestry (Scullion et al., 2016). However, there is no dedicated policy mix study specifically addressing social innovation nor social innovation in energy, as a search in Web of Science, utilizing the search criteria elaborated within SONNET for the construction of the Mendeley database revealed.

However, within SONNET it is assumed that the policy mix literature might be relevant for understanding and analysing socio-political issues in the context of social innovation in energy transitions. This literature acknowledges the complexity of real world climate and energy policy mixes, and its relevance for (system) innovation (Bouma et al., 2019; Rogge and Reichardt, 2016). Correspondingly, such new policy mix thinking in the context of sustainability transitions combines insights from various disciplines (Kern et al., 2019; Quitzow, 2015a), in particular economics (Sorrell and Sijm, 2003), innovation studies (Flanagan et al., 2011) and policy studies (Howlett et al., 2015). It thereby complements the predominant analysis of instrument interactions (Viguie and Hallegatte 2012) with other important aspects of climate and energy policy mixes.

In the most recent literature broad policy mixes are typically defined as “complex arrangements of multiple goals and means which, in many cases, have developed incrementally over many years.” (Kern and Howlett 2009, p. 395) or “as a combination of the three building blocks elements, processes and characteristics [...] Elements comprise the (i) policy strategy with its objectives and principal plans for achieving them and (ii) the instrument mix with its interacting policy instruments. The content of these elements is an outcome of policy processes. Both elements and processes can be described by their characteristics, including the consistency of elements, the coherence of processes, as well as the credibility and comprehensiveness of a policy mix. Finally, the policy mix can be delineated by several dimensions, including policy field, governance level, geography and time.” (Rogge and Reichardt 2016, p. 1622f).

A few points we know from this literature are:

- There are multiple policy rationales for preferring policy mixes to single policy instruments, such as carbon pricing as only climate policy instrument (Weber and Rohrer 2012, Jacobsson et al 2017).
- Climate and other sustainability transition policy strategies need to be credible to accelerate low-carbon, sustainable transitions (Rogge and Duetschke 2018, Rogge and Schleich 2018, Quitzow 2015).
- Comprehensive, balanced and consistent instrument mixes can help drive low-carbon transformative change (Constantini et al 2017, Schmidt and Sewerin 2019).

- Phasing out policies supporting carbon-intensive fuels, technologies or practises can accelerate low-carbon, sustainable (energy) transitions (Kivimaa and Kern 2016, David 2017, Cetkovic and Skjaereth 2019).
- To be successful climate policy mixes have to navigate resistance from vested interests (Geels 2014, Edmondson et al 2019; Roberts et al 2018, Meckling et al 2016, Kern and Rogge 2017).
- Greater focus in policy mixes on stakeholder interests and participation in policy making may help boost public acceptance (Wicki et al 2029).
- Accelerating decarbonisation and system transitions calls for enhancing policy coordination across governance levels and policy fields (Petersen and Heurkens, 2018).
- Systematic mapping of the policy mix is a precondition for policy mix analysis and design (Ossenbrink et al 2019).

What are the research gaps?

- While policy making and policies play a role in several SIE articles included in the SONNET Mendeley literature database tagged as having a socio-political focus, these do not explicitly assume the perspective of analyzing this through the lens of policy mixes.
- A review of the role of the implicit contributions on policy mixes for SIE does not exist, even though several studies arguable implicitly refer to policy mix thinking (without stating so), suggesting room for a systematic literature review.
- Multi-level policy mix analyses seem to focus on interactions between local and national level (Huang 2019, Matti et al 2017), whereas additional consideration of the interplay between local and European policy making apparently is less studied (to be confirmed through an in-depth literature review).
- Further gaps may be revealed when conducting a more thorough, systematic literature review of the socio-political studies in the Mendeley database.

What questions arise for SONNET?

Main research question:

- What is the role of SIE in EU, national, regional and local policy making? (see WP2, T2.4)

Research sub-questions:

- Which value added can be generated by framing SIE policies and politics within a broad policy mix thinking?
- Which role do policy mixes play in SIE processes, i.e. how can co-evolution between policy mixes and social innovation help explain SIE dynamics?
- How can SIE-initiatives and SIE intermediaries better connect with and harness policy dynamics at different governance levels (EU, national, regional and local energy policy making)?

What are key readings?

Note these core references are not specific to SIE (as none exist) and thus are also not included in the Mendeley database, but are key readings for the policy mixes for sustainability transitions literature more broadly.

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Annex 1: DoA Requirements

Information from proposal on SOCIO-POLITICAL issues / contributions

Relevant **Objectives 2 and 5:**

- O2 Identify and analyse enabling and impeding conditions for SIE processes, with a focus on socio-economic, socio-cultural (incl. gender) and **socio-political issues** and their interrelations with socio-technical aspects.
- O5 Encourage successful SIE through **co-creating socio-political strategies** to enhance governance arrangements and policy networks as well as SIE-related power and policy dynamics.

Possible examples for **enabling and impeding conditions** for SIE for socio-political issues:

- Policy instruments (& their design) in relevant policy fields (e.g. renewables feed-in tariffs, innovation support)
- Regulations (e.g. governing energy production, storage, data protection)
- Politics (e.g. policy networks, countervailing powers, political action, lobbying)

Socio-political contributions: What kind of alternative/novel governance arrangements and other means do SIE-initiatives create to address, for instance, issues of citizen participation, inclusion and power?

Three examples of possible means for trying to achieve sustainable energy goals related to socio-political contributions:

- Novel collaborative governance arrangements
- Novel or enhanced SIE actor networks for collective advocacy activities
- Novel decision making processes and structures within SIE-initiatives that can be used more widely

Work Package No.	2		Lead beneficiary					Fraunhofer ISI (1)					
WP title	<i>Socio-political: Socio-political issues of social innovation in energy transitions</i>												
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	AP
Short name of participant	ISI	DRIFT	UoS	GEM	ALK	ZHAW	ICLEI	MANN	ANTW	BRIS	GREN	WARS	BASE
Person months per participant:	9.5	8	5	1.5	6	1.5	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	-
Start month	9					End month			31				

Objectives: The aim of this work package is a comprehensive analysis of the socio-political issues through the three complementary lenses of governance arrangements, policy networks and power

dynamics of relevance for SIE. It sheds specific light on influential but often neglected aspects of innovation in governance arrangements, conflict and coordination in policy networks and power dynamics associated with SIE. It contributes towards *SONNET Objective 2*; foregrounding the socio-political enabling and impeding factors as well as *SONNET Objective 5* the design of socio-political strategies for encouraging SIE.

The **specific objectives** of WP 2 are:

- To investigate novel collaborative governance arrangements for SIE (T2.1)
- To analyse SIE policy networks enabling or impeding SIE (T2.2)
- To identify strategies for increasing the countervailing power of SIE to challenge the energy system (T2.3)
- To assess the role of SIE in EU, national, regional and local policy making (T2.4)

Description of work: WP2 draws on the literature review (T1.1), the typology (T1.2) as well as the conceptual framework (T1.3) as a basis for its work. It feeds the knowledge on new governance arrangements and governance learning (T2.1) as well as on enabling and impeding network structures and relations (T2.3) into WP4 and the city lab creation. All four outputs are included in the SIE toolkit (WP7) and made use of during SONNET events (T7.2). Finally, findings are fed into the inter- and transdisciplinary dialogue (T1.4), into the synthesis of cross-cutting issues (T1.5) and inform revising the conceptual framework and SIE typology (T1.6).

Task 2.1 Collaborative governance arrangements for SIE (M9-M16) (25%)

Lead: ALK, co-lead: ICLEI, supported by: Fraunhofer ISI and DRIFT, further involvement: all partners

This task explores collaborative governance arrangements for facilitating SIE. First, SONNET maps governance arrangements of city administrations in urban areas for harnessing the potentials of SIE for sustainable energy transitions. This initial map builds on the analysis of empirical literature on SIE (T1.1) and is complemented by interviews with city administration representatives of each of our six SONNET cities. Secondly, this task focuses on how city administrations learn to govern energy transitions through zooming in on how novel collaborative governance arrangements for enabling local sustainable energy transition processes are developed. Data about past governance learning processes of the six SONNET city administrations are gathered through a facilitated exchange between them in the form of a 'reflection circle' (M.17). The aim is to identify best practises for designing, implementing and learning from different ways of creating collaborative governance arrangements (D5).

Task 2.2 SIE Policy Networks for SIE (M9-M23) (29%)

Lead: Fraunhofer ISI, co-lead: DRIFT, supported by: GEM, ALK, ZHAW, further involvement: ICLEI.

This task aims to identify for each of our six cities the policy network in which our 30 SIE-initiatives (studied in-depth in T3.3) are embedded. A policy network analysis is conducted to analyse the relations between key actors at the local, regional, national and EU level (e.g. policy-makers, city administration actors, energy utilities, businesses and network organisations) and to identify enabling and impeding coordination structures for SIE-initiatives. Importantly, the approach also includes actors not directly linked to the energy sector but competing on city resources (e.g. money, space), or those who could profit from the multiple contributions of SIE. This task feeds network related questions to the interview protocol for T3.2, specifically related to relevant actors. In addition, this

task conducts 12-18 structured interviews per city with city officials, policy makers and intermediary organisations (i.e. organisation that support and advocate SIE), energy companies and networks of SIE in the six SONNET cities. To minimize time and effort of relevant actors these interviews also collect data for T2.3. While data collection happens locally, the data provides insights about relations well beyond city boundaries including regional, national and European level. The analysis provides insights into the surrounding policy network, but also identify collaborative and conflictual relations. The cross-country comparison of the resulting local policy networks serves as input to a city partner workshop (M.19) for discussing the existing and desirable role of the local policy networks in facilitating SIE. In close collaboration with the SONNET cities a toolkit is developed, which helps policy makers and SIE-initiatives to harness policy network structures in order to facilitate SIE.

Task 2.3 Power dynamics between SIE and dominant institutions (M9-M26) (26%)

Lead: DRIFT, co-lead: UoS, supported by Fraunhofer ISI and ICLEI.

This task focuses on understanding the power dynamics between SIE-initiatives and dominant institutions, as well as on identifying strategies for increasing the countervailing power of SIE initiatives. To this end, the task builds on insights from the literature review (T1.1) and takes additional documents (such as policy reports and position papers) as well as interview data with city officials, policy makers, intermediary organisations, energy companies, and networks of SIE from T2.2 (to this end, relevant questions are added to the interview protocol) as a starting point for a discourse analysis to understand power dynamics between SIE and dominant institutions. This analysis is shared during a ‘power lab’ session with SIE representatives (M.5) and acts as a starting point for co-designing strategies on how to increase the collective countervailing power of SIE to challenge energy institutions (D7).

T2.4 Assessing the role of SIE in EU, national, regional and local policy making (M25-M34) (20%)

Lead: Fraunhofer ISI, co-lead: UoS, supported by ICLEI, ALK and DRIFT, further involvement: all partners

This task assesses the role that SIE-initiatives or considerations regarding SIE play in EU, national, regional and local policymaking. This analysis focuses on the policies that were identified as relevant for enabling or impeding SIE (T3.4) specifically for those SIE types studied in WP 5 since these have the greatest potentials to further the goals of the Energy Union. Data about the focal policies comes from multiple sources such as consultation responses, newspapers, social media, and minutes of relevant policy meetings. The task further draws from the results of the policy network analysis (T2.2). The findings inform a multi-level, multi-actor policy dialogue with SIE intermediaries, SONNET city partners and relevant policy makers from all governance levels to discuss strategies for enhancing the role of SIE in EU, national, regional and local energy policy making (M.6). Based on the analysis and co-creation workshop a practical guide for SIE-initiatives and SIE intermediaries is developed on how to better connect with and harness policy dynamics at different governance levels (D8).

Deliverables	Delivery
D5 Report on encouraging SIE through collaborative governance arrangements	M16
D6 Towards a toolkit for harnessing policy networks for encouraging SIE in Europe	M23
D7 Encouraging SIE through strategies for increasing countervailing powers – a practical guide	M26
D8 Co-creating strategies for navigating multi-level policy dynamics to encourage SIE – reflections	M31

Research Brief #8: *Research brief on socio-economic issues of social innovation in energy.*

Wemyss, D., Hielscher, S., Vernay, Ranville, Struminska, M. & A. Dembek (2019)

Research briefing's relation to SONNET

SONNET differentiates between socio-economic, socio-cultural (incl. gender), and socio-political contributions of SIE and provides systematic insights into these, including how they interrelate with socio-technological aspects. For example, regarding socio-economic contributions SONNET looks into alternative/novel economic practices (Longhurst et al., 2016) – which include new investment activities (Debor, 2014) and associated business and service model innovations (Hiteva and Sovacool, 2017). These are plentiful as energy systems move into newly decarbonised, decentralised and digitalised configurations of energy generation, transmission, distribution, supply and consumption. SIE-initiatives might challenge the efficacy of existing markets and business models as the primary mechanism of economic allocation.

This briefing will highlight the recent literature related to the socio-economic themes relevant to SONNET, in order to begin to address the question: *“What kinds of alternative/novel economic practices and other means do SIE-initiatives create to address, for instance, issues of energy affordability and justice?”*

Reflections on conducting the review

To encompass the breadth of topics related to socio-economic issues of SIE, we have taken an interdisciplinary perspective, in particular, drawing on economics, management, geography, and sociology. The diverse themes that make up the socio-economic issues seem to be prevalent within many of the SONNET research foci i.e. SIE diversity, processes, contributions, success (or failure) and future potential of an SIE. Moreover, the socio-economic issue seems often to be linked to technical, political, social and cultural themes (i.e. socio-technical configurations), making it difficult to set clear boundaries between the socio-political, socio-cultural and socio-economic issue (see for instance the issues of energy justice or demand side management). Reflecting on the literature, it seems that most of the author(s) of the articles examine socio-economic issues related to a particular technology (e.g. smart meters) or SIE type (e.g. energy cooperative). Articles that look across technologies/ types do not seem to exist.

Overall, we understand that an underlying goal in SONNET is to uncover how to enhance social innovation in the energy sector, and that some barriers and drivers to achieve this are socio-economic. However, the SIE are non-traditional in their structure and functioning, sometimes disruptive, and potentially framed outside typical profit-oriented settings. Thus the socio-economic issues relevant to SONNET are unique, and potentially have not yet been investigated by academia. It also seems that there is an existing knowledge base in the SONNET consortium on some of these themes related to socio-economic issues.

What do we know from the literature?

The socio-economic team was wondering how to structure the literature review. We quickly realised when mapping the literature that we developed themes related to types of SIE or technology that they address (e.g. financial sustainability of energy cooperative or missing business models for smart developments). We were keen to create a structure that would move away from these thematic divisions to highlight the themes related to socio-economic issues more than the technologies/ types. We therefore came up with the following storyline to map our themes:

SIE have diverse motivations, goals, visions and problems that they want to address when initiating SIE activities and are multi-actor phenomena. They might do this with a business model in mind (or replicate one) – actively creating one or just through doing their thing develop one. Some people in the literature might argue that this business model is key for the longevity of the SIE and its activities. Through creating SIE activities and associated business models, SIE directly or indirectly might fill a gap, fit into, stretch, and/or challenge the current energy market. SIE can therefore ‘fit in’ or ‘challenge’ the current energy system through their activities and narratives. Incumbent energy actors (e.g. an energy provider) can react to these activities and associated business models and develop their own ‘SIE’.

We have therefore divided the literature in the following five themes. These themes are not exhaustive of the socio-economic issues to SIE, nor complete in their individual comprehensiveness, but they are a starting point for us to think about socio-economic issues in relation to the SONNET objectives.

1) Diverse motivations, and limitations to ambitions, of SIE to address local socio-economic issues

Across the documented cases of SIE, which are for the most part community-based renewable energy projects, the motivation and vision for the SIE differ widely (e.g. community economic regeneration). Literature however indicates that citizens participate in community-based renewable energy project primarily for hedonic motivations (Dóci, Vasileiadou, & Petersen, 2015) and to feel part of a local social (Kalkbrenner & Roosen, 2016; Seyfang, Park, & Smith, 2013). There may also be more strictly financial interests, such as reducing the local cost of electricity, or the will to address community economic well-being by providing new income streams and jobs (e.g. in Scotland (Macdonald, Glass, & Creamer, 2017)). However, while SIE have the potential to be more inclusive than other energy projects, they still may result in energy justice issues (e.g. imbalanced distributional effects due to capital investment costs) and social market failures (e.g. not all communities are sufficiently energy and policy literate to coordinate projects) (Clove, Mohr, & Brown, 2017; Hackett, 2016). Furthermore, the resulting benefits of a renewable energy project may not be fairly distributed, which may undermine the high ambitions of the project (Gorroño-Albizu, Sperling, & Djørup, 2019).

Looking more broadly, achieving economic value from a high electricity supply security can also be a vision of a community that experiences poor service quality or energy poverty (Islar & Busch, 2016; Llewellyn, Rohse, Day, & Fyfe, 2017; Sloot, Jans, & Steg, 2019). Initiating SIE from the grassroots can often address regional contextual challenges more effectively than an electric utility (Koirala, Koliou, Friege, Hakvoort, & Herder, 2016). This process can engage community members, and thus may highlight a pathway to social acceptance of renewable energy projects through community ownership and local realization of benefits (Bauwens & Devine-Wright, 2018; Klagge & Meister, 2018).

2) Sustaining the SIE over time: achieving financial sustainability

SIE are often driven by more social and environmental goals than traditional for-profit energy businesses, however this does not always remove the need for financial sustainability in order to support their activities. The literature focuses on energy cooperatives, but the following challenges could be relevant for other SIE forms as well: accessing subsidies; attracting investment; finding a customer segment and therein a compatible business and service models (Bere, Jones, Jones, & Munday, 2017; Branker, Shackles, & Pearce, 2011; Herbes, Brummer, Rognli, Blazejewski, & Gericke, 2017; Thapar, Sharma, & Verma, 2017). However, this highlights the tension that arises when a SIE may have to compromise in order to “fit” into the energy system which they are attempting to “challenge”. Traditional goals such as economic growth, may be replaced for social capital, and the concept of scaling and use of economies of scale may not be feasible.

From the literature, SIE have addressed these challenges through crowdfunding (Dilger, Jovanović, & Voigt, 2017) or hybrid ownership models between a community and private sector partner (Yildiz, 2014). Hybrid ventures (Blazek, 2016; Hatzl, Seebauer, Fleiss, & Posch, 2016) exhibit implementation challenges due to misaligned goals of the partners (social vs. economic capital), and it is uncertain to what extent these will fit in or challenge the existing system (Melville, Burningham, Christie, & Smallwood, 2018; Eadson & Foden, 2019; Goyal, Sergi, & Kapoor, 2014).

As mentioned in section B, the business model literature is strongly linked to specific technologies restructuring the energy system. Specifically concepts were found on differing notions of a) grids such as micro-grids, decentralised grids; (Gui, Diesendorf, & MacGill, 2017; Juntunen & Hyysalo, 2015; Scott, 2017) b) trading and managing energy such as P2P, DSM; (Alam, St-Hilaire, & Kunz, 2017; Liu, Wu, & Li, 2019; Singh et al., 2018) c) enabling technologies such as blockchain, storage (Brilliantova, Thurner, Brilliantov, & Thurner, 2019).

More upcoming literature seems to be linked to business models and market frameworks in smart energy developments, including developing business models (e.g. economic returns) and market frameworks (e.g. types of trading mechanisms, creation of what types of markets). Linked to this are differing notions of a) grids such as micro-grids, decentralised grids (Gui, Diesendorf, & MacGill, 2017; Juntunen & Hyysalo, 2015; Scott, 2017); b) trading and managing energy such as P2P, DSM (Alam, St-Hilaire, & Kunz, 2017; Liu, Wu, & Li, 2019; Singh et al., 2018); and c) enabling technologies such as blockchain, storage (Brilliantova, Thurner, Brilliantov, & Thurner, 2019). Some of this literature highlights the tension between the involved actors and citizen action resulting in competition to business.

3) Relation between SIE activities and the existing energy system (fit vs. stretch)

(Smith & Raven, 2012) proposed two ways through which a niche innovation can be empowered and diffused more broadly in a given regime. A niche can be empowered following a *fit and conform* strategy, where a niche innovation becomes competitive with mainstream socio-technical practices without having further impact on the prevailing regime. The main challenges for the niche organisation are not comprise on sustainability performance while becoming competitive with mainstream offers, and organising a

timely removal of niche protections in order to scale. A niche can also be empowered through a *stretch and transform* approach, where the niche contributes to undermining and re-shaping the prevailing regime. Here the organisation contribute to changing the selection environment so that it becomes more favourable to their diffusion.

Another field of literature also highlights the impact that incumbents have on defining acceptance behaviour of new technologies (Purtik & Arenas, 2019), which may indirectly open up pathways for SIE activities. However, this process is not always straightforward and can result in alienating or deterring communities (Macdonald, Glass, & Creamer, 2017).

4) SIE narratives and visions of alternative energy markets

A small amount of the literature is concerned with 'marcoeconomic' issues related to SIE. For instance, Hess (2011) has explored the history of the electricity industry through competing ideologies and practices (e.g. social liberalism, cooperativism, neoliberalism) and local antagonistic responses to energy marketplace restructuring throughout time. Hess (2011:1059) has adopted a field perspective "that assumes that "neoliberalism" can be more clearly understood when situated in a political field consisting of competing ideologies, policies, practices and agents" rather than just thinking about one dominant ideology. Similarly, Longhurst et al. (2016) have reported on alternative "economic" narratives grounded in examining social innovation initiatives. They have suggested that the narratives of these initiatives pose four critical questions: "What is the purpose of economic development? What are the preferred distributive mechanisms? Who governs the economy? What is the preferred form of economic organisation?"

Considering state and community negotiations surrounding the construction of energy markets in the UK, Eadson and Foden (2019) have drawn on Polanyi's work of the "double movement" to examine pro-market and pro-social action. This refers to "a philosophical commitment to deregulation, combined with a social responsibility (and electoral imperative) to mitigate its worst effects on people and the planet, creates challenges for governments." They cover four modes of energy market construction: "making policy, shaping existing markets, creating new markets and cultivating consumers", exploring how market and non-market logics conflict within policy formulation and enactment and the term "community" is used to govern parts of the energy markets.

There are two articles where the authors make use of two perspectives (i.e. degrowth and political economy) to examine energy transitions whilst looking at alternative practices (e.g. collective ownership) and citizen driven activities within them (Gunderson, Stuart, Petersen, & Yun, 2018; Haas, 2019). Gunderson et al. (2018) have argued that "a degrowth society with a collectively- owned energy system would allow for a reduction in total energy use as well as a lower ratio of fossil fuel energy to alternative energy".

5) Incumbent energy actors and their novel business models

Previous research discusses the role that entrepreneurial firms and incumbents play in the sustainable transformation of mass markets (Sarasini & Linder, 2017; Schaltegger, Lüdeke-Freund, & Hansen, 2016). While entrepreneurial organizations are more likely to develop innovative sustainable solutions, they often fail to reach the mass market and sometimes do not even have the intention to do so (Hockerts &

Wüstenhagen, 2010). However, when these organisations start to be perceived as a competitive threat by incumbents, incumbents may react by developing their own corporate sustainability initiatives. When incumbents do so, their large market presence allows them to reach mass markets (Hockerts & Wüstenhagen, 2010).

Scholars have also argued that transforming the energy sector will only be possible if the dominant logic of actors in the industry changes (Bidmon & Knab, 2018) and that business model innovation can be a critical element in inducing such change (Johnson & Suskewicz, 2009). This means that the ways actors in an industry define how they have to create, deliver and capture value has to change (Sabatier, Craig-Kennard, & Mangematin, 2012). This may take place through a process of co-evolution between entrepreneurial organisation and conventional incumbent (Schaltegger et al, 2016).

What are the gaps in the literature?

In this section, we would like to briefly point out a few gaps in the literature before thinking about them in more depth in the following section. Some of the gaps become apparent when looking at the five themes outlined above. At the moment, there seems to be less literature on how business models related to SIE activities sit (or not) within the existing energy system/ market. Although, there seems to be a growing literature on 'hybrid' SIE activities (and possible tensions that might develop between differing goals. These literatures also do not seem to question the role of hybrid SIE activities in fitting/ stretching/ challenging, or not, the energy system/ market.

Additional relevant gaps exist as less economically-driven SIE seem to be less represented in articles on socio-economic issues (this might also depend on our definition of socio-economic). While financial sustainability is often still relevant for these SIE, typologies of business models, investment strategies, etc. are hard to find. Also, only a few studies look at the economic capacity and social capital needed to create SIE initiatives (e.g. considering socio-economic differences between regions/ cities). The types of SIE investigated are also quite narrow and focus primarily on community-led initiatives.

Considering the multi-faceted motivations of SIE, little investigation has gone into non-energy goals/contributions of SIE that might help to broaden ways to think about success and contributions (i.e. values that SIE activities bring to local/ national energy goals). Similarly, reflection of SIE initiatives own understanding of socio-economic issues (i.e. how would they define them and argue how they address them) are not really explored in the literature.

Lastly, only a few papers are concerned with how the energy market (i.e. regulations and energy market condition (e.g. liberalization)) needs to change and the role of SIE within these changes.

What questions arise for SONNET?

Reflecting on the literature review, socio-economic issues have been studied in diverse ways, including micro and macro economic aspects (from SIE business models to narratives surrounding alternative energy practices/ systems beyond markets). The following themes may be relevant for SONNET activities.

SIE develop alternative energy practices. To be able to do this they need to create business models (where 'values' are different) that relate to their goals, motivations, etc.

- What kinds of alternative/novel economic practices and other means do SIE-initiatives create to address, for instance, issues of energy affordability and justice
- What role do investment strategies, ownership models and business models play for the emergence and development of SIE?
- How do SIE/ EU policymakers define success in relation to socio-economic issues? How do SIE actors/ academics currently measure this type of success (if they do)?
-

SIE need to sustain their activities over time.

- How do broader socio-economic conditions influence the processes of SIE?
- How are issues of economies of scale (or other related socio-economic ideas) relevant for the emergence, development, spread and potential scaling of SIE?

SIE business models can start to challenge the status quo energy market (or not), grounded in narratives and/ or practices.

- Which alternative economic narratives and practices exist (are being developed) within SIE? How are they mobilised to bring about change?
- What broader socio-economic issues do SIE address? E.g. Energy justice, renewable energy penetration, local energy efficiency, local sustainability issues (extending to food, mobility, safety, community, etc.)

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Research Brief #9: City Labs.

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Aim of the briefing: to define issues/ themes relevant for SONNET City Labs and to identify existing themes and gaps in the current literature, grounded on SONNET Mendeley literature database.

Preamble: Reflections on conducting the review

The term “city lab” and related concepts of “urban lab” or “living lab” are key terms for WP4 of SONNET project. As it describes the approach to research and action applied to solve different problems in various sectoral, national, and institutional context, it is highly flexible, but may also be ambiguous. Thus, one of the goals of the brief is to outline the main characteristics of diverse approaches to city labs and summarize the critical points in the debate around this methodology.

Within this literature review, we have explicitly focused on publications directly referring to lab methodology (tagged ‘lab’ in SONNET Mendeley library and/or containing ‘lab’ in the title or abstract). We supplemented the results with an additional search through bases (EBSCO) while using broadened search criteria (beyond peer reviewed journal articles). Our assumption was that research projects using collaborative, ‘lab-like’ approaches put a significant effort into preparation of practitioners-oriented publications, and that these materials can be of high relevance for SONNET project. Indeed, some of the materials found are of high value for the City Labs planning within SONNET. It particularly refers to Guidelines for Urban Labs (Scholl et al., 2017) and Lab Tool Kit prepared within URB@Exp (2014-2017) project, based on five city labs conducted in different European cities (Antwerp, Gratz, Leoben, Maastricht, Malmö).

Publications under inquiry exemplify different approaches to collaborative research and different understanding of labs, though “urban labs” or “city labs” were dominant concepts. Since all followed the **basic rule of co-creation oriented at collaborative experimenting and learning** (Scholl, 2018) we have analysed them jointly and refer to them as ‘lab-like’ approaches. Nevertheless, the differences between these approaches are important, and the useful typology of lab approaches can be found e.g. in (Scholl et al. 2017).

Within the brief we address two WP4 themes emphasized in SONNET proposal (p. 16): **1) collaborative methodology and its pitfalls** and **2) transdisciplinarity and co-production of knowledge**.

Regarding the first theme, we put an emphasis on balancing between the substantial focus on **collaborative problem solving** and **formal focus on institutional change** necessary to implement collaborative practices and employ collaboratively produced solutions. Drawing on the literature review, we suggest that the latter should be explicitly addressed in SONNET City Labs processes.

As to transdisciplinarity and co-production of knowledge, we focus on issues of inclusiveness and effectiveness and identify two distinct approaches: **(1) 'functionalist' approach**, underscoring cooperation and its role for effectiveness of solutions, and **(2) 'critical' approach** reflecting on (mainly power-related) tensions between inclusiveness and effectiveness (who decides what is good for whom?). Then we address sub-themes emerging from the literature review, all of which are exploring the processes of co-production of knowledge. These subthemes are the following: a) **learning and innovation**, b) **boundary position**, c) **emotions**. The last subtheme: d) **city lab as a governance model** is addressed in Socio-political brief.

**"Reflection note" – we ended up referring to a relatively large number of sources not listed in SONNET Mendeley library, so there might be a need to check the base once again (e.g. using other keywords than just 'lab'.*

THEME 1: Collaborative methodologies and their pitfalls

City (urban) labs (Scholl et al., 2018) belong to a family of experimental approaches, including living labs (Almirall & Wareham, 2011; Bergvall-Kåreborn & Ståhlbröst, 2009; Leminen, Westerlund, & Nyström, 2012), urban sustainability transition labs (Forrest & Wiek, 2014; Nevens, Frantzeskaki, Gorissen, & Loorbach, 2013), real-world laboratories (Schäpke, Stelzer, Bergmann, & Lang, 2016) and social innovation labs (Seyfang & Longhurst, 2016; Westley, Antadze, Riddell, Robinson, & Geobey, 2014). All these types of labs **aim to create space for transdisciplinary research, co-creation and experimenting with potential solutions to sustainability challenges** (Kemp & Scholl, 2016; Scholl et al., 2018). The diversified development of the field calls for increased coordination to enhance learning across experiments (Luederitz et al., 2017; Sengers, Berkhout, Wiczorek, & Raven, 2016; Voytenko, McCormick, Evans, & Schliwa, 2016), and for consideration of what forms of collaborative experimentation are best for which purposes.

(Scholl et al., 2018) based on the comparative analysis of city labs and the literature review, deliver a list of critical issues (pitfalls) involved in city labs practice. They specifically focus on transdisciplinary action research labelled as "transitioning of (urban lab) experiments". It consists

of four steps: 1) co-design of experiments, 2) setting explicit learning goals, 3) evaluating what has been learned, and 4) dissemination and embedding of lessons learned. Critically reflecting on the difficulties encountered in the implementation of the transitioning approach, they conclude that it **must be adapted when applied to urban labs focusing on sustainability transitions in institutional and governance systems rather than in socio-technical systems** (the focus of the original framework by Van den Bosch, 2010).

The pitfalls are gathered in four groups:

1. Diverging stakes. The city officials were more [than other partners] inclined to embrace the open-endedness required for a transition experiment relevant for learning about new forms of governance. In most cases, the non-governmental stakeholders engaged to implement their own, undiluted, preconceived ideas, and not to experiment and learn about new ways of working with the local government.
2. Lack of shared focus on strategic learning. Many actors find it hard to define beforehand what they want to learn from an experiment. The difference was especially stark between lab coordinators and other urban stakeholders.
3. Evaluation of learning hampered by too much focus on operational issues. The lack of an open design of the experiments and of jointly established strategic learning goals frequently resulted in a superficial focus on operational issues concerning the success of the experiment in its most immediate sense.
4. Missing links between labs and local government (that hampers integration of solutions). These missing links were a consequence of the problems encountered during the implementation of the previous steps: the different stakes in the goal of the experiments, the lack of clarity and shared focus on strategic learning about new forms of governance, and too much focus on operational issues when capturing the lessons.

Ultimately, when trying to disseminate and embed the lessons learned, the urban labs were confronted with the consequences of their outward-looking approach to the involvement of urban stakeholders, which often resulted in a lack of involvement of key local governance stakeholders, and difficulties in embedding of lessons learnt into practice.

Problem of dissemination and sustainability (durability) of solutions and procedures 'produced by labs' was addressed by several academics. In line with the above, in the paper reflecting on experiences from H2020 project, researchers suggest the problem can be addressed by '**gap analysis**' (Giannouli et al., 2018). Gaps relate here to the **underdeveloped institutional infrastructure linking labs with its organizational and institutional environment**, what in result hamper implantation of collaborative governance approaches and cross sectoral solutions

developed within labs. The gap analysis allows partners: (1) to identify gaps in their current institutional capacities and ways of working (tools, techniques, and practices), and (2) to identify inspirational examples of useful technical, spatial and institutional practices and tools they might use to fill these gaps or add to their current practices and tools. The gap analysis was thus instrumental in gaining a deeper understanding of local challenges by explicitly recognizing what was possible (reference cases) and what was lacking (current institutional capacities). In doing so, it also improved the mutual understanding among stakeholders of defining a common problem and the kind of skills, tools and resources they would have to use.

Another approach is proposed by (Gatta, Marcucci, & Le Pira, 2017), who suggest that implementation and dissemination of solutions and approaches developed in labs can be facilitated by **the mixed method approach**: combining lab approach with traditional descriptive approach and with modelling. A three-phase methodology enables experts to support local public authorities (i.e. the decision-makers) by: 1) increasing knowledge and understanding of the most innovative, promising context-specific policies (description based e.g. on desk research) 2) integrating policies in strategic urban planning via collaborative participation/governance processes; 3) developing an ex-ante, behaviourally consistent, financially robust and technically compatible assessment of shared policy mixes (modelling) while providing appropriate instruments to facilitate policy adoption.

Yet another perspective on 'implementation and dissemination' problem is the critical one, suggesting that one of the **major obstacles lies in power asymmetries reflected in dominant institutional arrangements**. (Strumińska-Kutra, 2016) proposes a methodological tool to deal with pitfalls of collaborative research related to three types of research-related relationships involving power: (1) between the participatory inquiry and its cultural, institutional, and social environment; (2) within 'the community' being studied, which itself is not homogeneous in terms of interests, values, and ability of their realization; and (3) between the researcher and 'the community'. She suggests that the tensions arise due to the use of the three mutually exclusive approaches of pragmatism, critical theory, and constructivism. Her claim is that this meta-theoretical inconsistency should be seen as a strength rather than a weakness. Following any approach in isolation would expose the researcher to the risk of opportunism (pragmatism), paternalism (critical theory), or relativism and therefore paralysis (constructivism). While used interchangeably, these three perspectives deliver checks and balances mechanisms enabling the researcher to escape those pitfalls and to conduct ethical and emancipatory inquiry.

What are the research gaps?

- *When to use 'lab-like' approaches and what type of labs are best suited to serve what purpose? (Scholl 2018)*

- *How to make City Labs more inclusive and socially responsible? (Scholl, Kemp 2016)*

What questions arise for SONNET?

- *How to address problem of implementation and dissemination within lab methodology?*

THEME 2: Transdisciplinarity of knowledge and co-creation

In the literature under review, **concept of knowledge co-creation seems to be more popular than transdisciplinarity**. Despite the fact that the concept of transdisciplinary action research (TAR) is used explicitly (Scholl et al., 2018), the distinction that attracts most attention is the one between different types of partners (participants) bringing their perspectives to the labs, rather than distinctions between disciplines (e.g. partners from public, private and civic sector: Evans & Karvonen, 2011; Voytenko et al., 2016). The discipline-related distinctions are usually expressed indirectly. For example, the technological fix of the mainstream energy and innovation research is criticized for not recognizing contradictions between political, ecological, socio-economic and technological interests (Claude, Ginestet, Bonhomme, Moulene, & Escadeillas, 2017; Chatterton, Owen, Cutter, Dymski, & Unsworth, 2018), that is, for disregarding the perspectives typically accounted for by sociology, anthropology, political sciences.

Some researchers suggest that overlooking of these aspects leads to perpetuating neoliberal agenda and individualization of responsibility (e.g., focus on 'smartness' determines rather high socio-economic status of groups under research, while focus on consumers redirects attention from systemic problems; Levenda, 2019). Critique is also directed at overlooking of cultural, reflexive aspects of innovation, e.g. by focusing on what technology does to people instead of what people do to technology (Schwartz et al., 2015). Another example is focusing on how innovative solutions enable users to change their practices, for example in the area of mobility, instead of focusing on innovative vehicles and services' design (Liedtke, Baedeker, Hasselkuß, Rohn, & Grinewitschus, 2015; Sopjani, Stier, Ritzen, Hesselgren, & Georen, 2019).

Alternative approach to the one criticized above stress more active role of users, often omitted by City Lab designers.

"(...) users do not just contribute by demonstrating their needs or through elicitation of information to benefit innovation. Rather, they influence processes of technology development and implementation by demanding more sustainable alternatives, generating expectations and legitimacy, learning how to use new sustainable alternatives and adopting these alternatives to change their own behaviour. In contrast, users can also

challenge expectations of providers by resisting to be controlled or to change their behaviour in response to new ideas, or by hacking the design for their own purpose” (Sopjani et al., 2019).

‘Functionalist’ approach:

In the reviewed literature, **co-creation of knowledge is framed as a response to the failure of traditional research approaches**. Failures arise due to: 1) inability to integrate different kinds of knowledge: from private, public and civic sector, and therefore inability to address the complexities of social problems (Claude et al., 2017); 2) technocratic bias, overlooking diversity of axiological orientations, economic status, cultural backgrounds (Haider, Kopp, & Pajones, 2016; Levenda, 2019; Schwartz et al., 2015). The justification evolving around input based- (democracy and inclusiveness of the process) and output based-legitimacy (effectiveness of solutions) is typical for both participatory/collaborative governance approaches ((Ferlie, Lynn Jr, Lynn, Pollitt, & Lynn, 2005; Mayntz, 2001) and action based approaches in social research (Greenwood & Levin, 2007). In this sense **co-creation is also treated as a tool to increase social acceptance and effectiveness of policy making** and/or solutions developed within the process (be it process of inquiry or planning process).

In some papers, the capacity to balance inclusiveness and effectiveness, and to produce legitimacy, is perceived as labs’ characteristic and strength. The examples vary in terms of topics and contexts, from Claude et al. (2017) on involving many participants in the thermal refurbishment of a historical district that helped to design ‘efficient and acceptable solution’ and in the long run to reduce energy poverty; Cole & Srivastava (2013) and Dvarioniene et al. (2015) on trust building effects of stakeholders involvement in labs that are ‘investment in the future’; Joller & Varblane (2016) on labs as tools for increasing users acceptance, to Liedtke et al. (2012) on labs as integrated technological socio-economic approach to enable optimised interaction of production and consumption.

Among these ‘functionalist’ approaches some analysis are focused on identifying key actors of collaborative innovation development and innovation networks in (living) lab context. (Nyström, Leminen, Westerlund, & Kortelainen, 2014) proposed four categories of living labs: utilizer-, enabler-, provider-, and user community-driven, based on identifying the most active actor in the beginning of the living lab, that later becomes the driver of the actions. In the research on sustainable mobility (Joller & Varblane, 2016; Sopjani et al., 2019) it is also suggested to involve non-users as an important source of insight. (Juujärvi & Pessa, 2013) suggest that at different stages of labs’ development, different actors should take over steering role, since different competences are needed at each stage (see also Scholl et al., 2018).

‘Critical’ approach:

On the other hand, there are authors arguing that not enough attention has been paid to the **tensions between the interests and goals of different participants** of the labs (Kemp & Scholl, 2016; Scholl et al., 2018; Weiland, Bleicher, Polzin, Rauschmayer, & Rode, 2017). Some of them (Scholl et al., 2018) see the need to transform methodology of the labs in order to address these problems openly (*see THEME 1: Collaborative methodologies*). Variety of goals and interests is amplified by power asymmetries among stakeholders. For example, while reflecting on smart and sustainable city experiments (Levenda, 2019) makes three points. First, urban experimentation offers opportunities for entrepreneurial forms of governance, at the level of the individual and the city, to take hold through smart and sustainable cities agenda. Second, the transformative potential of smart and sustainable cities agenda is undercut by a focus on governing individual consumption instead of systemic change. Third, these techno-fix agendas often produce inequities that are overshadowed in public discourse by the spectacle of sustainability and smartness. Levenda's case of smart energy grids and labs illustrates how the focus on economic growth, demonstration of technological efficiency, and individual consumption habits limits **the power of experimentation for transformative change**.

When used within a critical perspective, labs become tools for challenging dominant discourses and power arrangements (Chatterton et al., 2018; Scholl et al., 2018). 'Less radical' academics recommend taking these discourses and power arrangements into account (instead of directly confronting them like the 'radicals'), since they pose barriers for dissemination of solutions and practices developed within labs. For example, they point at certain formal requirements for decision making that limit a potential arising from trust building collaborations within labs and impeded learning processes (Pettersson, Westerdahl, & Hansson, 2018a). Those authors emphasize that an enforced collaboration, being performed half-heartedly (Ansell & Gash, 2008), impedes trust building (Thomson & Perry, 2006) and understanding of the partner organisations' roles and goals (Hrelja, Pettersson, & Westerdahl, 2016).

Another way to address institutional inertia is a production of **holistic approaches**. For example: integrated energy planning (de Boer & Zuidema, 2015) connects energy theme with spatial planning to accommodate the integration of energy systems within their physical and socioeconomic landscapes; INTENSSS-PA project (HORIZON 2020) uses living lab methodology to provide 'a holistic energy plan, which goes beyond a blueprint for allocating renewable technologies and is based on the involvement of the wider community'. This approach includes aspects such as: development of spatial concepts, new co-creating strategies, business cases, societal alliances and institutional changes and formats (Giannouli et al., 2018). Project's important goal is to build, develop and implement a human and institutional capacity building process related to sustainable energy planning and energy projects implementation (rather superficially addressed in Giannouli 2018). Chatterton (2018) suggests that the capacity and potency building, empowering the potential of co-production in city labs requires more analysis.

Disciplinary affiliations:

Among disciplines delivering background for lab-like approaches prominent place is given to **sustainability science**, in particular its process-oriented approaches with a strong focus on implementation, participation and conducting research on societal change processes towards more sustainable practices (Kemmis, 2010; Scholl et al., 2018; Wittmayer & Schöpke, 2014). Strong links are made to management (niche management and transition management). Some authors supplement this with another management and organizational theories of learning, strategic learning and collaborative learning (Pettersson, Westerdahl, & Hansson, 2018b; Scholl et al., 2018). Significant number of publications is embedded in energy and mobility research and planning theories.

SUB-THEME 1: Learning and innovation

Most of the papers emphasize experimental and learning-oriented nature of lab-like approaches. In many instances, **learning and innovation becomes an explicitly expressed goal of labs** (e.g. Evans & Karvonen, 2011; Kemp & Scholl, 2016; Scholl et al., 2018). Some of the authors focus on the role of academic partners in facilitating learning processes (Evans & Karvonen, 2011; Pettersson et al. 2018a, 2018b), some trace process of learning in labs. For example, Seppo, Leminen & Westerlund (2017) propose to focus on living labs not as a methodology but as an arrangement that, while using appropriate tools, can significantly foster the emergence of innovation. They depict four ways those tools are used in living labs and suggest the ways in which they can be used to reorganize innovation in an open innovation model. The dimensions of the framework include the innovation process (“predefined, linear” versus “iterative, nonlinear”) and the usage of tools (“standardized” versus “customized”).

Scholl et al. (2018) indicate that learning (especially strategic learning) remains an ‘under-communicated’ aim of the city lab, and, to a certain extent, the aim mainly for public officials rather than for other stakeholders, who usually participate to ‘get things done’. Pettersson et al. (2018) argue that even those interested in learning, usually learn on the individual and team level, but not necessarily at the organizational level, especially if the second loop learning is concerned. These problems relate to the dissemination and sustainability of lab results (*see THEME: Collaborative methodologies*).

Authors call for further exploration of the link between collaboration and learning. Joller & Varblane (2016) suggest that in order to achieve transformative innovation, a **culture of purposeful experimentation** must be fostered. Such transitions are only possible if a critical mass of social actors is ready to conceive and commit to radical transformative change at an early stage, well before the outcome seems inevitable. This involves thinking beyond the incremental optimisation of existing systems— as typically encouraged by dominant everyday political and commercial pressures (Scrase & Smith, 2009).

Considering the above, Scholl et al. (2018) call for more case studies looking into innovative potential of city labs. In order to corroborate methods potential in this regard, **comparative research is necessary**. They hypothesize that city labs which are set up with the explicit purpose of experimenting with new forms of urban planning will achieve more than those that merely stimulate local projects in urban development (Pettersson, Westerdahl, & Hansson, 2018b). Authors like Chatterton et al. (2018) emphasize the need for comparison from yet another angle. They suggest that looking beyond locally based initiatives prevents falling into a trap of geographical naiveté, attempting to solve local problems without reference to broader social, historical and spatial contexts. The comparative perspective should also encompass a question: 'who decides about what should be learnt?' Those using co-production labs need to ensure that activities are focused on genuine empowerment rather than tokenism. Measures to counteract these deficits include making productive links to other international examples and initiatives, as well as ensuring equality of input between participants and sectors when conceiving and implementing processes and outcomes. External verification from independent bodies can be useful here, e.g. to establish more prototypes, so potential problems can be addressed and a more rigorous evidence base for future action can be outlined (Chatterton, 2018).

SUB-THEME 2: Boundary organizations and boundary work

As Scholl and Kemp (2016) describe it, the term refers to the management of institutional junctions through a co-production process in which formal responsibilities are de-emphasised in the direct cooperation process and re-emphasised towards the outside world and at critical moments in the cooperation process (cf. Hoppe, 2010; Kemp & Rotmans, 2009). Boundary work helps to overcome institutional boundaries between science and policy, between city administration and societal actors, and between different types of knowledge holders. It is done by accepting different types of knowledge as relevant. Therefore, the concept of boundary work actually addresses the question: '**how to organize collaborative learning?**' The authors consider further work on the nature of boundary work and its usefulness as a theoretical concept to be desirable.

A fruitful direction of analysis is the concept of institutional work, that is purposeful actions directed at maintenance, transformation and disruption of institutions (Lawrence & Suddaby, 2006). Institutional perspective rarely uses action based, collaborative approaches for the analysis of practice work and identity work related to implementation of collaborative governance (Struminska-Kutra 2018, see also Chatterton 2018, and *SUBTHEME Labs as a governance mode in WP2 brief*).

SUB-THEME 3: Emotions

Institutional reconfigurations and ambiguities raise status problems and institutional anxieties about loss of power (Chatterton et al., 2018; Struminska-Kutra, 2018; Kraatz & Block, 2017). Whereas previous studies on co-production have commented on the motivations and experiences of 'citizen co-producers' (Van Eijk & Steen, 2014), Chattertons' et al. (2018) work focused on the experiences of professionals in co-production. The authors suggest that:

“more relaxed institutional boundaries can impact on certain professional personae, creating a sense of vulnerability or being overwhelmed due to the potential uncertainties involved. Some professions require clear organization and outcomes. Forms of co-production that are more anarchic and disorganized and encourage (quick) failure from which people can learn may be disorientating. This can create vulnerability with respect to justifying participation to professional peers and managers less committed to a co-production ethos.” (p.12)

In this regard an important point is made by some innovation and learning research: experimenting requires feeling of security (for its possible sources see (Strumińska-Kutra, 2018).

What are the research gaps?

- *Effectiveness of labs is rather assumed than exemplified, most of the research reflects on the process while neglecting outcomes (see also Vroom et al 2015)*
- *The role of different disciplines is not expressed directly. There is little reflection on how ontological, epistemological and methodological traditions contribute to lab methodologies and collaborative methodologies*
- *Trust building potential of labs is rather assumed than systematically researched*

What questions arise for SONNET?

- *What is the potential of city labs to generate long-lasting social innovation in energy across different national and urban contexts? (--> focus on evaluation of the outcome)*
- *What factors related to socio-political or institutional context enable long-lasting impact?*

Research sub-questions:

- *What is the role of collaboration in learning, especially for double loop learning? When does double loop learning happens?*
- *To what extent are city labs comparable across different cities (gap analysis)?*

- *What are the factors conditioning the embedding of the lessons learnt from City Labs in SONNET cities? To what extent can they be scaled up to other cities?*
- *What is the role of knowledge exchange between the cities? What are the mechanisms of such knowledge exchange?*
- *What is the role of knowledge derived from different academic disciplines in the design of a city lab and its outcome analysis (evaluation process)? What is the potential of the results to become a part of disciplinary knowledge (e.g. in sociology, management, sustainability science)?*

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